

Block-Wise and Block-Bordered Magic Squares Generated by Pythagorean Triples: Orders 3 to 47

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Abstract

*Pythagorean triples are very famous in the literature of mathematics. Special kind of magic squares can be constructed based **Pythagorean triples** and vice-versa. Recently, author studied different kind of magics squares including **block-wise**, **block-bordered**, **block-wise-bordered** etc. In this paper, some special kind of Pythagorean triples are generated, and then based on these Pythagorean triples magic squares of orders 3 to 47 are constructed with **consecutive odd numbers** entries. The **odd order magic squares** also lead to **consecutive natural number** entries with same sum resulting in **Pythagorean triples**. We know that we can always write **block-wise** magic squares of any order except for the orders of type p and $2p$, where p is a prime number. In these type of cases, **block-bordered** magic squares are constructed. These are of orders 10, 11, 13, 17, 19, 22, 23, 26, 29, 31, 34, 37, 38, 41, 43, 46 and 47. In other cases, **block-wise** magic squares are constructed. These are of orders 8, 9, 12, 15, 16, 18, 20, 21, 24, 25, 27, 28, 30, 32, 33, 35, 36, 39, 40, 42, 44 and 45. In another work, **Pythagorean triples** are generated based on **consecutive odd number** entries magic squares starting from 1.*

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1 Pythagoras Theorem

Pythagoras Theorem is well-known in the literature. By Pythagoras theorem it is understood that

$$a^2 + b^2 = c^2.$$

For simplicity, let's write it as (a, b, c) . If we talk of distances, then the numbers a , b and c are real positive numbers, otherwise they can be any real number. The **Pythagorean triple** $(3, 4, 5)$ is understood as $3^2 + 4^2 = 5^2$. Let's consider the following well-known procedure [1] to write Pythagorean triples:

$$F(m, n) := m^2 - n^2$$

$$\begin{aligned}G(m, n) &:= 2mn \\ H(m, n) &:= m^2 + n^2\end{aligned}\tag{1}$$

Then we can easily check that

$$\begin{aligned}F(m, n)^2 + G(m, n)^2 &= (m^2 - n^2)^2 + (2mn)^2 \\ &= m^4 - 2m^2n^2 + n^4 + 4m^2n^2 \\ &= m^4 + 2m^2n^2 + n^4 \\ &= (m^2 + n^2)^2 = H(m, n)^2.\end{aligned}$$

We shall use frequently the formula (1) to find **Pythagorean triples** in subsequent section. In this paper, our aim is to write procedures to bring **Pythagorean triples** in two different ways. One as a general way and second by use of the formula given in (1). Based on these **Pythagorean triples** we shall generate procedure for magic squares of orders 3 to 99. All the magic squares are with odd numbers entries. The odd order magic squares are written in two different ways. One with odd order entries and another with natural numbers entries. The prime number and its double order magic squares are written as block-bordered magic squares and other orders are written as block-wise magic squares.

2 Generating Pythagorean Triples

This section give simplified procedure to write Pythagorean triples. It is divided in different blocks.

2.1 First Procedure

This procedure don't used the formula given in (1). It is just based on simple trick.

Result 1. *Let's write a number 100 as sum of two parts in such a way that the one of the part is a perfect square. See below:*

1. $100 = 19 + 81$	4. $100 = 64 + 36$	7. $100 = 91 + 09$
2. $100 = 36 + 64$	5. $100 = 75 + 25$	8. $100 = 96 + 04$
3. $100 = 51 + 49$	6. $100 = 84 + 16$	9. $100 = 99 + 01$

(2)

We observe that the right hand sides of the expression (2) are formed by two sums, where the last two digits are perfect squares written in decreasing order. Even though, 100 can also be written as $100 + 00 + 100$. Let's consider a difference of squares between the terms of r.h.s. with 1 in the front of perfect square term. Then this difference is again a perfect square multiple of 20 resulting in Pythagorean triples. See below:

$$\begin{aligned}181^2 - 019^2 &= 180^2 \Rightarrow 019^2 + 180^2 = 181^2 \Rightarrow (019, 180, 181) \\164^2 - 036^2 &= 160^2 \Rightarrow 036^2 + 160^2 = 164^2 \Rightarrow (036, 160, 164) \\149^2 - 051^2 &= 140^2 \Rightarrow 051^2 + 140^2 = 149^2 \Rightarrow (051, 140, 149) \\136^2 - 064^2 &= 120^2 \Rightarrow 064^2 + 120^2 = 136^2 \Rightarrow (064, 120, 136) \\125^2 - 075^2 &= 100^2 \Rightarrow 075^2 + 100^2 = 125^2 \Rightarrow (075, 100, 125) \\116^2 - 084^2 &= 080^2 \Rightarrow 084^2 + 080^2 = 116^2 \Rightarrow (084, 080, 116) \\109^2 - 091^2 &= 060^2 \Rightarrow 091^2 + 060^2 = 109^2 \Rightarrow (091, 060, 109) \\104^2 - 096^2 &= 040^2 \Rightarrow 096^2 + 040^2 = 104^2 \Rightarrow (096, 040, 104) \\101^2 - 099^2 &= 020^2 \Rightarrow 099^2 + 020^2 = 101^2 \Rightarrow (099, 020, 101)\end{aligned}\tag{3}$$

Above procedure is only for 1 and 0. Let's extend it for further squares. The first line with (300, 400, 500) also is added. See below

$$\begin{aligned}500^2 - 300^2 &= 400^2 \Rightarrow 300^2 + 400^2 = 500^2 \Rightarrow (300, 400, 500) \\481^2 - 319^2 &= 360^2 \Rightarrow 319^2 + 360^2 = 481^2 \Rightarrow (319, 360, 481) \\464^2 - 336^2 &= 320^2 \Rightarrow 336^2 + 320^2 = 464^2 \Rightarrow (336, 320, 464) \\449^2 - 351^2 &= 280^2 \Rightarrow 351^2 + 280^2 = 449^2 \Rightarrow (351, 280, 449) \\436^2 - 364^2 &= 240^2 \Rightarrow 364^2 + 240^2 = 436^2 \Rightarrow (364, 240, 436) \\425^2 - 375^2 &= 200^2 \Rightarrow 375^2 + 200^2 = 425^2 \Rightarrow (375, 200, 425) \\416^2 - 384^2 &= 160^2 \Rightarrow 384^2 + 160^2 = 416^2 \Rightarrow (384, 160, 416) \\409^2 - 391^2 &= 120^2 \Rightarrow 391^2 + 120^2 = 409^2 \Rightarrow (391, 120, 409) \\404^2 - 396^2 &= 080^2 \Rightarrow 396^2 + 080^2 = 404^2 \Rightarrow (396, 080, 404) \\401^2 - 399^2 &= 040^2 \Rightarrow 399^2 + 040^2 = 401^2 \Rightarrow (399, 040, 401)\end{aligned}\tag{4}$$

$$\begin{aligned}1000^2 - 800^2 &= 600^2 \Rightarrow 800^2 + 600^2 = 1000^2 \Rightarrow (800, 600, 1000) \\981^2 - 819^2 &= 540^2 \Rightarrow 819^2 + 540^2 = 981^2 \Rightarrow (819, 540, 981) \\964^2 - 836^2 &= 480^2 \Rightarrow 836^2 + 480^2 = 964^2 \Rightarrow (836, 480, 964) \\949^2 - 851^2 &= 420^2 \Rightarrow 851^2 + 420^2 = 949^2 \Rightarrow (851, 420, 949) \\936^2 - 864^2 &= 360^2 \Rightarrow 864^2 + 360^2 = 936^2 \Rightarrow (864, 360, 936) \\925^2 - 875^2 &= 300^2 \Rightarrow 875^2 + 300^2 = 925^2 \Rightarrow (875, 300, 925) \\916^2 - 884^2 &= 240^2 \Rightarrow 884^2 + 240^2 = 916^2 \Rightarrow (884, 240, 916) \\909^2 - 891^2 &= 180^2 \Rightarrow 891^2 + 180^2 = 909^2 \Rightarrow (891, 180, 909) \\904^2 - 896^2 &= 120^2 \Rightarrow 896^2 + 120^2 = 904^2 \Rightarrow (896, 120, 904) \\901^2 - 899^2 &= 060^2 \Rightarrow 899^2 + 060^2 = 901^2 \Rightarrow (899, 060, 901)\end{aligned}$$

(5)

$$\begin{aligned}1700^2 - 1500^2 &= 800^2 \Rightarrow 1500^2 + 800^2 = 1700^2 \Rightarrow (1500, 800, 1700) \\1681^2 - 1519^2 &= 720^2 \Rightarrow 1519^2 + 720^2 = 1681^2 \Rightarrow (1519, 720, 1681) \\1664^2 - 1536^2 &= 640^2 \Rightarrow 1536^2 + 640^2 = 1664^2 \Rightarrow (1536, 640, 1664) \\1649^2 - 1551^2 &= 560^2 \Rightarrow 1551^2 + 560^2 = 1649^2 \Rightarrow (1551, 560, 1649) \\1636^2 - 1564^2 &= 480^2 \Rightarrow 1564^2 + 480^2 = 1636^2 \Rightarrow (1564, 480, 1636) \\1625^2 - 1575^2 &= 400^2 \Rightarrow 1575^2 + 400^2 = 1625^2 \Rightarrow (1575, 400, 1625) \\1616^2 - 1584^2 &= 320^2 \Rightarrow 1584^2 + 320^2 = 1616^2 \Rightarrow (1584, 320, 1616) \\1609^2 - 1591^2 &= 240^2 \Rightarrow 1591^2 + 240^2 = 1609^2 \Rightarrow (1591, 240, 1609) \\1604^2 - 1596^2 &= 160^2 \Rightarrow 1596^2 + 160^2 = 1604^2 \Rightarrow (1596, 160, 1604) \\1601^2 - 1599^2 &= 080^2 \Rightarrow 1599^2 + 080^2 = 1601^2 \Rightarrow (1599, 080, 1601)\end{aligned}$$

(6)

$$\begin{aligned}2600^2 - 2400^2 &= 1000^2 \Rightarrow 2400^2 + 1000^2 = 2600^2 \Rightarrow (2400, 1000, 2600) \\2581^2 - 2419^2 &= 0900^2 \Rightarrow 2419^2 + 0900^2 = 2581^2 \Rightarrow (2419, 0900, 2581) \\2564^2 - 2436^2 &= 0800^2 \Rightarrow 2436^2 + 0800^2 = 2564^2 \Rightarrow (2436, 0800, 2564) \\2549^2 - 2451^2 &= 0700^2 \Rightarrow 2451^2 + 0700^2 = 2549^2 \Rightarrow (2451, 0700, 2549) \\2536^2 - 2464^2 &= 0600^2 \Rightarrow 2464^2 + 0600^2 = 2536^2 \Rightarrow (2464, 0600, 2536) \\2525^2 - 2475^2 &= 0500^2 \Rightarrow 2475^2 + 0500^2 = 2525^2 \Rightarrow (2475, 0500, 2525) \\2516^2 - 2484^2 &= 0400^2 \Rightarrow 2484^2 + 0400^2 = 2516^2 \Rightarrow (2484, 0400, 2516) \\2509^2 - 2491^2 &= 0300^2 \Rightarrow 2491^2 + 0300^2 = 2509^2 \Rightarrow (2491, 0300, 2509) \\2504^2 - 2496^2 &= 0200^2 \Rightarrow 2496^2 + 0200^2 = 2504^2 \Rightarrow (2496, 0200, 2504) \\2501^2 - 2499^2 &= 0100^2 \Rightarrow 2499^2 + 0100^2 = 2501^2 \Rightarrow (2499, 0100, 2501)\end{aligned}\tag{7}$$

$$\begin{aligned}3700^2 - 3500^2 &= 1000^2 \Rightarrow 3500^2 + 1000^2 = 3700^2 \Rightarrow (3500, 1200, 3700) \\3681^2 - 3519^2 &= 1080^2 \Rightarrow 3519^2 + 1080^2 = 3681^2 \Rightarrow (3519, 1080, 3681) \\3664^2 - 3536^2 &= 0960^2 \Rightarrow 3536^2 + 0960^2 = 3664^2 \Rightarrow (3536, 0960, 3664) \\3649^2 - 3551^2 &= 0840^2 \Rightarrow 3551^2 + 0840^2 = 3649^2 \Rightarrow (3551, 0840, 3649) \\3636^2 - 3564^2 &= 0720^2 \Rightarrow 3564^2 + 0720^2 = 3636^2 \Rightarrow (3564, 0720, 3636) \\3625^2 - 3575^2 &= 0600^2 \Rightarrow 3575^2 + 0600^2 = 3625^2 \Rightarrow (3575, 0600, 3625) \\3616^2 - 3584^2 &= 0480^2 \Rightarrow 3584^2 + 0480^2 = 3616^2 \Rightarrow (3584, 0480, 3616) \\3609^2 - 3591^2 &= 0360^2 \Rightarrow 3591^2 + 0360^2 = 3609^2 \Rightarrow (3591, 0360, 3609) \\3604^2 - 3596^2 &= 0240^2 \Rightarrow 3596^2 + 0240^2 = 3604^2 \Rightarrow (3596, 0240, 3604) \\3601^2 - 3599^2 &= 0120^2 \Rightarrow 3599^2 + 0120^2 = 3601^2 \Rightarrow (3599, 0120, 3601)\end{aligned}\tag{8}$$

$$\begin{aligned}5000^2 - 4800^2 &= 1400^2 \Rightarrow 4800^2 + 1400^2 = 5000^2 \Rightarrow (4800, 1400, 5000) \\4981^2 - 4819^2 &= 1260^2 \Rightarrow 4819^2 + 1260^2 = 4981^2 \Rightarrow (4819, 1260, 4981) \\4964^2 - 4836^2 &= 1120^2 \Rightarrow 4836^2 + 1120^2 = 4964^2 \Rightarrow (4836, 1120, 4964) \\4949^2 - 4851^2 &= 0980^2 \Rightarrow 4851^2 + 0980^2 = 4949^2 \Rightarrow (4851, 0980, 4949) \\4936^2 - 4864^2 &= 0840^2 \Rightarrow 4864^2 + 0840^2 = 4936^2 \Rightarrow (4864, 0840, 4936) \\4925^2 - 4875^2 &= 0700^2 \Rightarrow 4875^2 + 0700^2 = 4925^2 \Rightarrow (4875, 0700, 4925) \\4916^2 - 4884^2 &= 0560^2 \Rightarrow 4884^2 + 0560^2 = 4916^2 \Rightarrow (4884, 0560, 4916) \\4909^2 - 4891^2 &= 0420^2 \Rightarrow 4891^2 + 0420^2 = 4909^2 \Rightarrow (4891, 0420, 4909) \\4904^2 - 4896^2 &= 0280^2 \Rightarrow 4896^2 + 0280^2 = 4904^2 \Rightarrow (4896, 0280, 4904) \\4901^2 - 4899^2 &= 0140^2 \Rightarrow 4899^2 + 0140^2 = 4901^2 \Rightarrow (4899, 0140, 4901)\end{aligned}\tag{9}$$

$$\begin{aligned}6500^2 - 6300^2 &= 1600^2 \Rightarrow 6300^2 + 1600^2 = 6500^2 \Rightarrow (6300, 1600, 6500) \\6481^2 - 6319^2 &= 1440^2 \Rightarrow 6319^2 + 1440^2 = 6481^2 \Rightarrow (6319, 1440, 6481) \\6464^2 - 6336^2 &= 1280^2 \Rightarrow 6336^2 + 1280^2 = 6464^2 \Rightarrow (6336, 1280, 6464) \\6449^2 - 6351^2 &= 1120^2 \Rightarrow 6351^2 + 1120^2 = 6449^2 \Rightarrow (6351, 1120, 6449) \\6436^2 - 6364^2 &= 0960^2 \Rightarrow 6364^2 + 0960^2 = 6436^2 \Rightarrow (6364, 0960, 6436) \\6425^2 - 6375^2 &= 0800^2 \Rightarrow 6375^2 + 0800^2 = 6425^2 \Rightarrow (6375, 0800, 6425) \\6416^2 - 6384^2 &= 0640^2 \Rightarrow 6384^2 + 0640^2 = 6416^2 \Rightarrow (6384, 0640, 6416) \\6409^2 - 6391^2 &= 0480^2 \Rightarrow 6391^2 + 0480^2 = 6409^2 \Rightarrow (6391, 0480, 6409) \\6404^2 - 6396^2 &= 0320^2 \Rightarrow 6396^2 + 0320^2 = 6404^2 \Rightarrow (6396, 0320, 6404) \\6401^2 - 6399^2 &= 0160^2 \Rightarrow 6399^2 + 0160^2 = 6401^2 \Rightarrow (6399, 0160, 6401)\end{aligned}\tag{10}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 8200^2 - 8000^2 &= 1800^2 \Rightarrow 8000^2 + 1800^2 = 8200^2 \Rightarrow (8000, 1800, 8200) \\
 8181^2 - 8019^2 &= 1620^2 \Rightarrow 8019^2 + 1620^2 = 8181^2 \Rightarrow (8019, 1620, 8181) \\
 8164^2 - 8036^2 &= 1440^2 \Rightarrow 8036^2 + 1440^2 = 8164^2 \Rightarrow (8036, 1440, 8164) \\
 8149^2 - 8051^2 &= 1260^2 \Rightarrow 8051^2 + 1260^2 = 8149^2 \Rightarrow (8051, 1260, 8149) \\
 8136^2 - 8064^2 &= 1080^2 \Rightarrow 8064^2 + 1080^2 = 8136^2 \Rightarrow (8064, 1080, 8136) \\
 8125^2 - 8075^2 &= 0900^2 \Rightarrow 8075^2 + 0900^2 = 8125^2 \Rightarrow (8075, 0900, 8125) \\
 8116^2 - 8084^2 &= 0720^2 \Rightarrow 8084^2 + 0720^2 = 8116^2 \Rightarrow (8084, 0720, 8116) \\
 8109^2 - 8091^2 &= 0540^2 \Rightarrow 8091^2 + 0540^2 = 8109^2 \Rightarrow (8091, 0540, 8109) \\
 8104^2 - 8096^2 &= 0360^2 \Rightarrow 8096^2 + 0360^2 = 8104^2 \Rightarrow (8096, 0360, 8104) \\
 8101^2 - 8099^2 &= 0180^2 \Rightarrow 8099^2 + 0180^2 = 8101^2 \Rightarrow (8099, 0180, 8101)
 \end{aligned} \tag{11}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 10100^2 - 9900^2 &= 2000^2 \Rightarrow 9900^2 + 2000^2 = 10100^2 \Rightarrow (9900, 2000, 10100) \\
 10081^2 - 9919^2 &= 1800^2 \Rightarrow 9919^2 + 1800^2 = 10081^2 \Rightarrow (9919, 1800, 10081) \\
 10064^2 - 9936^2 &= 1600^2 \Rightarrow 9936^2 + 1600^2 = 10064^2 \Rightarrow (9936, 1600, 10064) \\
 10049^2 - 9951^2 &= 1400^2 \Rightarrow 9951^2 + 1400^2 = 10049^2 \Rightarrow (9951, 1400, 10049) \\
 10036^2 - 9964^2 &= 1200^2 \Rightarrow 9964^2 + 1200^2 = 10036^2 \Rightarrow (9964, 1200, 10036) \\
 10025^2 - 9975^2 &= 1000^2 \Rightarrow 9975^2 + 1000^2 = 10025^2 \Rightarrow (9975, 1000, 10025) \\
 10016^2 - 9984^2 &= 0800^2 \Rightarrow 9984^2 + 0800^2 = 10016^2 \Rightarrow (9984, 0800, 10016) \\
 10009^2 - 9991^2 &= 0600^2 \Rightarrow 9991^2 + 0600^2 = 10009^2 \Rightarrow (9991, 0600, 10009) \\
 10004^2 - 9996^2 &= 0400^2 \Rightarrow 9996^2 + 0400^2 = 10004^2 \Rightarrow (9996, 0400, 10004) \\
 10001^2 - 9999^2 &= 0200^2 \Rightarrow 9999^2 + 0200^2 = 10001^2 \Rightarrow (9999, 0200, 10001)
 \end{aligned} \tag{12}$$

We observe that the first block, i.e., (3) is with 9 triples, while other 9 blocks are with 10 triples in each case.

Remark 2.1. *Analyzing the 10 blocks, (3) to (12), we observe the following:*

- (i) *The last column in each case is constant as a square, i.e., 01, 04, 09, 16, 25, 36, 49, 64, 81 and 100. The fixed element in each block is 1 minus of square element of third columns, i.e., 0, 3, 8, 15, 24, 35, 48, 63, 80 and 99.*
- (ii) *The numbers given in item (i) can be understood as formula: $a01^2 - (a - 1)99^2$, where a is a perfect square, for examples, $1601^2 - 1599^2$, $4901^2 - 4899^2$, etc.*

2.2 Second Procedure

The triples given in (3)-(12) can also be obtained by use of formula given in (1). These are given below in 10 blocks

Result 2.

- (i) Let's consider $m = 10$ and vary n , i.e., $n = 9, 8, 7, 6, 5, 4, 3, 2, 1$ in (1), we get respectively, the Pythagorean triples given (3).
- (ii) Let's consider $m = 20$ and vary n , i.e., $n = 10, 9, 8, 7, 6, 5, 4, 3, 2, 1$ in (1), we get respectively, the Pythagorean triples given (4).
- (iii) Let's consider $m = 30$ and vary n , i.e., $n = 10, 9, 8, 7, 6, 5, 4, 3, 2, 1$ in (1), we get respectively, the Pythagorean triples given (5).
- (iv) Let's consider $m = 40$ and vary n , i.e., $n = 10, 9, 8, 7, 6, 5, 4, 3, 2, 1$ in (1), we get respectively, the Pythagorean triples given (6).
- (v) Let's consider $m = 50$ and vary n , i.e., $n = 10, 9, 8, 7, 6, 5, 4, 3, 2, 1$ in (1), we get respectively, the Pythagorean triples given (7).
- (vi) Let's consider $m = 60$ and vary n , i.e., $n = 10, 9, 8, 7, 6, 5, 4, 3, 2, 1$ in (1), we get respectively, the Pythagorean triples given (8).
- (vii) Let's consider $m = 70$ and vary n , i.e., $n = 10, 9, 8, 7, 6, 5, 4, 3, 2, 1$ in (1), we get respectively, the Pythagorean triples given (9).
- (viii) Let's consider $m = 80$ and vary n , i.e., $n = 10, 9, 8, 7, 6, 5, 4, 3, 2, 1$ in (1), we get respectively, the Pythagorean triples given (10).
- (ix) Let's consider $m = 90$ and vary n , i.e., $n = 10, 9, 8, 7, 6, 5, 4, 3, 2, 1$ in (1), we get respectively, the Palindromic triples given (11).
- (x) Let's consider $m = 100$ and vary n , i.e., $n = 10, 9, 8, 7, 6, 5, 4, 3, 2, 1$ in (1), we get respectively, the Palindromic triples given (12)

Finally, in view of Result 1 or Result 2 we have following 99 **Pythagorean Triples**:

- | | | | |
|---------------------|----------------------|-----------------------|------------------------|
| 1. (19, 180, 181) | 14. (364, 240, 436) | 27. (891, 180, 909) | 40. (2400, 1000, 2600) |
| 2. (36, 160, 164) | 15. (375, 200, 425) | 28. (896, 120, 904) | 41. (2419, 900, 2581) |
| 3. (51, 140, 149) | 16. (384, 160, 416) | 29. (899, 60, 901) | 42. (2436, 800, 2564) |
| 4. (64, 120, 136) | 17. (391, 120, 409) | 30. (1500, 800, 1700) | 43. (2451, 700, 2549) |
| 5. (75, 100, 125) | 18. (396, 80, 404) | 31. (1519, 720, 1681) | 44. (2464, 600, 2536) |
| 6. (84, 80, 116) | 19. (399, 40, 401) | 32. (1536, 640, 1664) | 45. (2475, 500, 2525) |
| 7. (91, 60, 109) | 20. (800, 600, 1000) | 33. (1551, 560, 1649) | 46. (2484, 400, 2516) |
| 8. (96, 40, 104) | 21. (819, 540, 981) | 34. (1564, 480, 1636) | 47. (2491, 300, 2509) |
| 9. (99, 20, 101) | 22. (836, 480, 964) | 35. (1575, 400, 1625) | 48. (2496, 200, 2504) |
| 10. (300, 400, 500) | 23. (851, 420, 949) | 36. (1584, 320, 1616) | 49. (2499, 100, 2501) |
| 11. (319, 360, 481) | 24. (864, 360, 936) | 37. (1591, 240, 1609) | 50. (3500, 1200, 3700) |
| 12. (336, 320, 464) | 25. (875, 300, 925) | 38. (1596, 160, 1604) | 51. (3519, 1080, 3681) |
| 13. (351, 280, 449) | 26. (884, 240, 916) | 39. (1599, 80, 1601) | 52. (3536, 960, 3664) |

53. (3551, 840, 3649)	65. (4875, 700, 4925)	77. (6391, 480, 6409)	89. (8099, 180, 8101)
54. (3564, 720, 3636)	66. (4884, 560, 4916)	78. (6396, 320, 6404)	90. (9900, 2000, 10100)
55. (3575, 600, 3625)	67. (4891, 420, 4909)	79. (6399, 160, 6401)	91. (9919, 1800, 10081)
56. (3584, 480, 3616)	68. (4896, 280, 4904)	80. (8000, 1800, 8200)	92. (9936, 1600, 10064)
57. (3591, 360, 3609)	69. (4899, 140, 4901)	81. (8019, 1620, 8181)	93. (9951, 1400, 10049)
58. (3596, 240, 3604)	70. (6300, 1600, 6500)	82. (8036, 1440, 8164)	94. (9964, 1200, 10036)
59. (3599, 120, 3601)	71. (6319, 1440, 6481)	83. (8051, 1260, 8149)	95. (9975, 1000, 10025)
60. (4800, 1400, 5000)	72. (6336, 1280, 6464)	84. (8064, 1080, 8136)	96. (9984, 800, 10016)
61. (4819, 1260, 4981)	73. (6351, 1120, 6449)	85. (8075, 900, 8125)	97. (9991, 600, 10009)
62. (4836, 1120, 4964)	74. (6364, 960, 6436)	86. (8084, 720, 8116)	98. (9996, 400, 10004)
63. (4851, 980, 4949)	75. (6375, 800, 6425)	87. (8091, 540, 8109)	99. (9999, 200, 10001)
64. (4864, 840, 4936)	76. (6384, 640, 6416)	88. (8096, 360, 8104)	

3 Generating Magic Squares

Recently, the author [5, 6, 7] worked on magic squares connected with Pythagorean triples. In these, works the sum of all entries of a magic square are always a perfect square. The work in Pythagorean triples and patterns are done by author in [8, 9, 10, 11, 12]. On the other side the author worked extensively on magic squares in different situations, such as, block-wise [13, 14, 18, 19], block-bordered [15, 16, 18], block-wise-bordered [19, 20, 21], etc. In this we shall try to extend and revise previous works done separately. In this work, we shall construct magic squares based on **Pythagorean triples** generated in Section 2.

Let's write a Procedure studied by author in [5, 6] to generate magic squares from the Pythagorean triples:

Result 3. *In a Pythagorean triple, (a, b, c) if any of the difference*

$$c - b \text{ or } c - a, \quad c > b, \quad c > a,$$

*is a perfect square greater than or equal to 9, then we can always write a **perfect square sum magic square**.*

Let us consider

$$(a, b, c) \Rightarrow \{\text{order of magic square, first member of sequence,} \\ \text{last member of sequence, magic sum, sum of all members of a magic square}\}. \quad (13)$$

For example,

$$\{15, 8, 17\} \Rightarrow \{3, 17, 33, 75, 225\}. \quad (14)$$

The above representation (14) is understood as:

- 3 $\Rightarrow$ Order of a magic square;
- 17 $\Rightarrow$ First member of the sequence;
- 33 $\Rightarrow$ Last member of the sequence;
- 75 $\Rightarrow$ Magic sum;
- 225 $\Rightarrow$ Sum of all members of the magic square, is a perfect square, $225 = 15^2$.

In this case, the 9 **consecutive odd numbers** generating magic square are 17, 19, 21, 23, 25, 27, 29, 31 and 33.

Result 4. To reach the result appearing in equation (14) we used the following formula:

$$(a, b, c) \Rightarrow \left\{ \left\{ \frac{c^2 - a^2}{\sqrt{c-a}}, c^2 - a^2, 2a + 1, 2c - 1, \sqrt{c-a} \right\}, \left\{ \frac{c^2 - b^2}{\sqrt{c-b}}, c^2 - b^2, 2b + 1, 2c - 1, \sqrt{c-b} \right\} \right\} \quad (15)$$

Result 3 is good for testing the existence of magic square, whilst Result 4 is useful for calculating the details of magic square. Using the Procedure given in 15, we have following distributions for the construction of magic squares based on 99 Pythagorean triples given in (3)-(12):

- | | | | |
|---------------------|--|-----------------------|---|
| 1. (19, 180, 181) | $\Rightarrow \{1, 281, 297, 867, 2601 = 51^2\}$ | 20. (800, 600, 1000) | $\Rightarrow \{20, 1201, 1999, 32000, 640000 = 800^2\}$ |
| 2. (36, 160, 164) | $\Rightarrow \{2, 241, 271, 1024, 4096 = 64^2\}$ | 21. (819, 540, 981) | $\Rightarrow \{21, 1081, 1961, 31941, 670761 = 819^2\}$ |
| 3. (51, 140, 149) | $\Rightarrow \{3, 281, 297, 867, 2601 = 51^2\}$ | 22. (836, 480, 964) | $\Rightarrow \{22, 961, 1927, 31768, 698896 = 836^2\}$ |
| 4. (64, 120, 136) | $\Rightarrow \{4, 241, 271, 1024, 4096 = 64^2\}$ | 23. (851, 420, 949) | $\Rightarrow \{23, 841, 1897, 31487, 724201 = 851^2\}$ |
| 5. (75, 100, 125) | $\Rightarrow \{5, 201, 249, 1125, 5625 = 75^2\}$ | 24. (864, 360, 936) | $\Rightarrow \{24, 721, 1871, 31104, 746496 = 864^2\}$ |
| 6. (84, 80, 116) | $\Rightarrow \{6, 161, 231, 1176, 7056 = 84^2\}$ | 25. (875, 300, 925) | $\Rightarrow \{25, 601, 1849, 30625, 765625 = 875^2\}$ |
| 7. (91, 60, 109) | $\Rightarrow \{7, 121, 217, 1183, 8281 = 91^2\}$ | 26. (884, 240, 916) | $\Rightarrow \{26, 481, 1831, 30056, 781456 = 884^2\}$ |
| 8. (96, 40, 104) | $\Rightarrow \{8, 81, 207, 1152, 9216 = 96^2\}$ | 27. (891, 180, 909) | $\Rightarrow \{27, 361, 1817, 29403, 793881 = 891^2\}$ |
| 9. (99, 20, 101) | $\Rightarrow \{9, 41, 201, 1089, 9801 = 99^2\}$ | 28. (896, 120, 904) | $\Rightarrow \{28, 241, 1807, 28672, 802816 = 896^2\}$ |
| 10. (30, 40, 50) | $\Rightarrow \{10, 1, 199, 9000, 90000 = 300^2\}$ | 29. (899, 60, 901) | $\Rightarrow \{29, 121, 1801, 27869, 808201 = 899^2\}$ |
| 11. (319, 360, 481) | $\Rightarrow \{11, 721, 961, 9251, 101761 = 319^2\}$ | 30. (1500, 800, 1700) | $\Rightarrow \{30, 1601, 3399, 75000, 2250000 = 1500^2\}$ |
| 12. (336, 320, 464) | $\Rightarrow \{12, 641, 927, 9408, 112896 = 336^2\}$ | 31. (1519, 720, 1681) | $\Rightarrow \{31, 1441, 3361, 74431, 2307361 = 1519^2\}$ |
| 13. (351, 280, 449) | $\Rightarrow \{13, 561, 897, 9477, 123201 = 351^2\}$ | 32. (1536, 640, 1664) | $\Rightarrow \{32, 1281, 3327, 73728, 2359296 = 1536^2\}$ |
| 14. (364, 240, 436) | $\Rightarrow \{14, 481, 871, 9464, 132496 = 364^2\}$ | 33. (1551, 560, 1649) | $\Rightarrow \{33, 1121, 3297, 72897, 2405601 = 1551^2\}$ |
| 15. (375, 200, 425) | $\Rightarrow \{15, 401, 849, 9375, 140625 = 375^2\}$ | 34. (1564, 480, 1636) | $\Rightarrow \{34, 961, 3271, 71944, 2446096 = 1564^2\}$ |
| 16. (384, 160, 416) | $\Rightarrow \{16, 321, 831, 9216, 147456 = 384^2\}$ | 35. (1575, 400, 1625) | $\Rightarrow \{35, 801, 3249, 70875, 2480625 = 1575^2\}$ |
| 17. (391, 120, 409) | $\Rightarrow \{17, 241, 817, 8993, 152881 = 391^2\}$ | 36. (1584, 320, 1616) | $\Rightarrow \{36, 641, 3231, 69696, 2509056 = 1584^2\}$ |
| 18. (396, 80, 404) | $\Rightarrow \{18, 161, 807, 8712, 156816 = 396^2\}$ | 37. (1591, 240, 1609) | $\Rightarrow \{37, 481, 3217, 68413, 2531281 = 1591^2\}$ |
| 19. (399, 40, 401) | $\Rightarrow \{19, 81, 801, 8379, 159201 = 399^2\}$ | 38. (1596, 160, 1604) | $\Rightarrow \{38, 321, 3207, 67032, 2547216 = 1596^2\}$ |

based on distributions given in (16).

Below are magic squares of orders 3 to 47 constructed according to values given in (16). These are based on **consecutive odd number** entries not necessarily starting with 1. In case of **odd order magic squares**, we can also write **consecutive natural number** entries.

4 Magic Square of Order 3

This subsection brings two types of magic squares with same magic sum. One with **consecutive odd numbers** entries and another with **consecutive natural numbers** entries.

4.1 Consecutive Odd Number Entries

According to distribution

$$(51, 140, 149) \Rightarrow \{3, 281, 297, 867, 2601 = 51^2\},$$

given in 3rd line of (16), we can construct a magic square of order 3 of **consecutive odd numbers**, (281, 283, ..., 295, 297). See below:

Example 4.1. A magic square of order 3 for the entries (281, 283, ..., 295, 297) is given by

			867
291	281	295	867
293	289	285	867
283	297	287	867
867	867	867	867

The above magic square is of magic sum $S_{3 \times 3} = 867$, and the total number of entries is a perfect square sum, i.e., $T_9 := 2601 = 51^2$. It satisfies the **Pythagoras Theorem** given as $51^2 + 140^2 = 149^2$.

4.2 Consecutive Natural Number Entries

The magic square given in Example 4.1 is constructed with **consecutive odd numbers** entries (281, 283, ..., 295, 297). Still, we can get same magic square sum with **consecutive natural numbers** considering entries as 285, 286, 287, 288, 289, 290, 291, 292, 293. See below magic square:

Example 4.2. A magic square of order 3 for the **consecutive natural numbers** entries 285, 286, 287, 288, 289, 290, 291, 292, 293 is given by

			867
288	293	286	867
287	289	291	867
292	285	290	867
867	867	867	867

The magic squares of order 3 given in Examples 4.1 and 4.2 are with same magic sums, i.e., $S_{3 \times 3} := 867$.

5 Magic Square of Order 4

According to distribution

$$(64, 120, 136) \Rightarrow \{4, 241, 271, 1024, 4096 = 64^2\},$$

given in 4th line of (16), we can construct a **pandiagonal** magic square of order 4 using **consecutive odd numbers**, (241, 243, ..., 269, 271). See below:

Example 5.1. A *pandiagonal* magic square of order 4 for the entries (241, 243, ..., 269, 271) is given by

		1024	1024	1024	1024
	253	263	241	267	1024
1024	243	265	255	261	1024
1024	271	245	259	249	1024
1024	257	251	269	247	1024
	1024	1024	1024	1024	1024

The above magic square is of magic sum $S_{4 \times 4} = 1024$, and total number of entries is a perfect square sum, i.e., $T_{16} := 4096 = 64^2$. It satisfies the **Pythagoras Theorem** given as $64^2 + 120^2 = 136^2$.

6 Magic Square of Order 5

This subsection brings two types of magic squares with same magic sum. One with **consecutive odd numbers** entries and another with **consecutive natural numbers** entries.

6.1 Consecutive Odd Number Entries

According to distribution

$$(75, 100, 125) \Rightarrow \{5, 201, 249, 1125, 5625 = 75^2\},$$

given in 5th line of (16), we can construct a **pandiagonal** magic square of order 5 using **consecutive odd numbers**, (201, 203, ..., 247, 249). See below:

Example 6.1. A **pandiagonal** magic square of order 5 for the entries (201, 203, ..., 247, 249) is given by

		1125	1125	1125	1125	1125
	201	213	225	237	249	1125
1125	235	247	209	211	223	1125
1125	219	221	233	245	207	1125
1125	243	205	217	229	231	1125
1125	227	239	241	203	215	1125
	1125	1125	1125	1125	1125	1125

The above magic square is of magic sum $S_{5 \times 5} = 1125$, and total number of entries is a perfect square sum, i.e., $T_{25} := 5625 = 75^2$. It satisfies the **Pythagoras Theorem** given as $75^2 + 100^2 = 125^2$.

6.2 Consecutive Natural Number Entries

The magic square given in Example 6.1 is constructed with consecutive entries (201, 203, ..., 247, 249). Still, we can get same magic square sum with **consecutive natural numbers** entries considering as (213, 214, ..., 235, 237). See below magic square:

Example 6.2. A **pandiagonal** magic square of order 5 for the **consecutive natural numbers** entries (213, 214, ..., 235, 237) is given by

		1125	1125	1125	1125	1125
	213	219	225	231	237	1125
1125	230	236	217	218	224	1125
1125	222	223	229	235	216	1125
1125	234	215	221	227	228	1125
1125	226	232	233	214	220	1125
	1125	1125	1125	1125	1125	1125

The magic squares of order 5 given in Examples 6.1 and 6.2 are with same magic sums, i.e., $S_{5 \times 5} := 1125$.

7 Magic Square of Order 6

According to distribution

$$(84, 80, 116) \Rightarrow \{6, 161, 231, 1176, 7056 = 84^2\},$$

given in 6th line of (16), we can construct a magic square of order 6 using **consecutive odd numbers**, (161, 263, ..., 229, 231). See below:

Example 7.1. A magic square of order 6 for the entries (161, 205, ..., 229, 231) is given by

						1176
161	205	215	227	193	175	1176
217	173	229	187	201	169	1176
183	171	185	213	221	203	1176
223	191	167	207	179	209	1176
197	225	181	165	219	189	1176
195	211	199	177	163	231	1176
1176	1176	1176	1176	1176	1176	1176

The above magic square is of magic sum $S_{6 \times 6} = 1176$, and total number of entries is a perfect square sum, i.e., $T_{36} := 7056 = 84^2$. It satisfies the **Pythagoras Theorem** given as $84^2 + 80^2 = 116^2$.

8 Magic Square of Order 7

This subsection brings two types of magic squares with same magic sum. One with **consecutive odd numbers** entries and another with **consecutive natural numbers** entries.

8.1 Consecutive Odd Number Entries

According to distribution

$$(91, 60, 109) \Rightarrow \{7, 121, 217, 1183, 8281 = 91^2\},$$

given in 7^{th} line of (16), we can construct a **pandiagonal** magic square of order 7 using **consecutive odd numbers**, (121, 123, ..., 215, 217). See below.

Example 8.1. A **pandiagonal** magic square of order 7 for the entries (121, 123, ..., 215, 217) is given by

		1183	1183	1183	1183	1183	1183	1183
	121	137	153	169	185	201	217	1183
1183	199	215	133	135	151	167	183	1183
1183	165	181	197	213	131	147	149	1183
1183	145	161	163	179	195	211	129	1183
1183	209	127	143	159	1183	177	193	1183
1183	189	191	207	125	141	157	173	1183
1183	155	171	187	203	205	123	139	1183
	1183	1183	1183	1183	1183	1183	1183	1183

The above magic square is of magic sum $S_{7 \times 7} = 1183$, and total number of entries is a perfect square sum, i.e., $T_{49} := 8281 = 91^2$. It satisfies the **Pythagoras Theorem** given as $91^2 + 60^2 = 109^2$.

8.2 Consecutive Odd Number Entries

The magic square given in Example 8.1 is constructed with consecutive odd numbers entries (121, 123, ..., 215, 217). Still, we can get same magic square sum with consecutive natural number entries considering as (145, 146, ..., 192, 193). See below magic square:

Example 8.2. A *pandiagonal* magic square of order 7 for the *consecutive natural numbers* entries (145, 146, ..., 192, 193) is given by

		1183	1183	1183	1183	1183	1183	1183
	145	153	161	169	177	185	193	1183
1183	184	192	151	152	160	168	176	1183
1183	167	175	183	191	150	158	159	1183
1183	157	165	166	174	182	190	149	1183
1183	189	148	156	164	172	173	181	1183
1183	179	180	188	147	155	163	171	1183
1183	162	170	178	186	187	146	154	1183
	1183	1183	1183	1183	1183	1183	1183	1183

The magic squares of order 7 given in Examples 8.1 and 8.2 are with same magic sums, i.e., $S_{7 \times 7} := 1183$.

9 Magic Square of Order 8

According to distribution

$$(96, 40, 104) \Rightarrow \{8, 81, 207, 1152, 9216 = 96^2\},$$

given in 8th line of (16), we can construct a **pandiagonal** magic square of order 8 using **consecutive odd numbers**, (81, 83, ..., 205, 207). See below:

Example 9.1. A *block-wise pandiagonal* magic square of order 8 for the entries (81, 83, ..., 205, 207) is given by

		1152	1152	1152	1152	1152	1152	1152	1152
	81	201	135	159	97	185	119	175	1152
1152	143	151	89	193	127	167	105	177	1152
1152	153	129	207	87	169	113	191	103	1152
1152	199	95	145	137	183	111	161	121	1152
1152	83	203	133	157	99	187	117	173	1152
1152	141	149	91	195	125	165	107	179	1152
1152	155	131	205	85	171	115	189	101	1152
1152	197	93	147	139	181	109	163	123	1152
	1152	1152	1152	1152	1152	1152	1152	1152	1152

The above magic square is of magic sum $S_{8 \times 8} = 1152$, and total number of entries is a perfect square sum, i.e., $T_{64} := 9216 = 96^2$. It satisfies the **Pythagoras Theorem** given as $96^2 + 40^2 = 104^2$.

10 Magic Square of Order 9

This subsection brings two types of magic squares with same magic sum. One with **consecutive odd numbers** entries and another with **consecutive natural numbers** entries.

10.1 Consecutive Odd Number Entries

According to distribution

$$(99, 20, 101) \Rightarrow \{9, 41, 201, 1089, 9801 = 99^2\},$$

given in 9th line of (16), we can construct a **pandiagonal** magic square of order 8 using **consecutive odd numbers**, (41, 43, ..., 199, 201). See below:

Example 10.1. A *block-wise pandiagonal* magic square of order 9 for the entries (41, 43, ..., 199, 201) is given by

		1089	1089	1089	1089	1089	1089	1089	1089	1089
	41	65	89	99	23	147	151	175	199	1089
1089	97	121	145	149	173	197	45	69	93	1089
1089	153	177	201	43	67	91	95	119	143	1089
1089	83	53	59	141	111	117	193	163	169	1089
1089	139	109	115	191	161	167	87	57	63	1089
1089	195	165	171	85	55	61	137	107	113	1089
1089	71	77	47	129	135	105	181	187	157	1089
1089	127	133	103	179	185	155	75	81	51	1089
1089	183	189	159	73	79	49	125	131	101	1089
	1089	1089	1089	1089	1089	1089	1089	1089	1089	1089

The above magic square is of magic sum $S_{9 \times 9} = 1089$, and total number of entries is a perfect square sum, i.e., $T_{81} := 1089 \times 9 = 9801 = 99^2$. It satisfies the **Pythagoras Theorem** given as $99^2 + 20^2 = 101^2$.

This subsection brings two types of magic squares with same magic sum. One with **consecutive odd numbers** entries and another with **consecutive natural numbers** entries.

10.2 Consecutive Natural Number Entries

The magic square given in Example 10.1 is constructed with **consecutive odd numbers** entries (41, 43, ..., 199, 201). Still, we can get same magic square sum with **consecutive natural numbers** entries considering as (81, 82, ..., 160, 161). See below magic square:

Example 10.2. A *block-wise pandiagonal* magic square of order 9 for the **consecutive natural numbers** entries (81, 82, ..., 160, 161) is given by

		1089	1089	1089	1089	1089	1089	1089	1089	1089
	88	129	146	141	104	118	116	157	90	1089
1089	117	143	103	92	115	156	145	87	131	1089
1089	158	91	114	130	144	89	102	119	142	1089
1089	94	108	161	147	83	133	122	136	105	1089
1089	132	149	82	107	121	135	160	93	110	1089
1089	137	106	120	109	159	95	81	134	148	1089
1089	100	123	140	153	98	112	128	151	84	1089
1089	111	155	97	86	127	150	139	99	125	1089
1089	152	85	126	124	138	101	96	113	154	1089
	1089	1089	1089	1089	1089	1089	1089	1089	1089	1089

The magic squares of order 9 given in Examples 10.1 and 10.2 are with same magic sums, i.e., $S_{9 \times 9} := 1089$.

11 Magic Square of Order 10

According to distribution

$$(300, 400, 500) \Rightarrow \{10, 801, 999, 9000, 90000 = 300^2\},$$

given in 10th line of (16), we can construct a magic square of order 10 of **consecutive odd numbers**, 801, 803, ..., 997, 999. See below:

Example 11.1. A magic square of order 10 for the entries 801, 803, ..., 997, 999 is given by

										9000
801	959	929	993	877	843	895	971	905	827	9000
995	823	817	931	979	947	909	865	881	853	9000
893	961	845	957	831	869	987	919	923	815	9000
939	913	975	867	803	981	857	829	951	885	9000
967	997	903	821	889	935	945	813	859	871	9000
825	875	887	819	953	911	963	841	989	937	9000
949	891	879	965	855	837	933	983	807	901	9000
917	847	991	883	921	805	839	955	873	969	9000
851	809	833	915	985	899	861	927	977	943	9000
863	925	941	849	907	973	811	897	835	999	9000
9000	9000	9000	9000	9000	9000	9000	9000	9000	9000	9000

Above magic square is with magic sum, $S_{10 \times 10} := 9000$ with entries sum a perfect square sum, i.e., $T_{100} := 90000 = 300^2$. It satisfies the **Pythagoras Theorem** given as $300^2 + 400^2 = 500^2$.

11.1 Block-Bordered Magic Squares of Order 10

Example 11.2. The **block-bordered** magic square of order 10 with inner part as **block-wise** magic square of order 8 for the **consecutive odd numbers** entries 801, 803, ..., 997, 999 is given by

981	971	831	967	835	827	807	995	803	983
825	893	915	837	955	877	931	853	939	975
977	843	949	899	909	859	933	883	925	823
821	963	845	907	885	947	861	923	869	979
991	901	891	957	851	917	875	941	867	809
801	895	913	839	953	879	929	855	937	999
985	841	951	897	911	857	935	881	927	815
813	961	847	905	887	945	863	921	871	987
989	903	889	959	849	919	873	943	865	811
817	829	969	833	965	973	993	805	997	819

The above **block-bordered** magic square of order 10 is with inner part as **block-wise pandiagonal** magic square of order 8 with blocks of **pandiagonal** magic squares of order 4 having equal magic sums. Below are respective magic sums:

$$S_{10 \times 10} = 9000$$

$$S_{8 \times 8} = 7200$$

$$S_{4 \times 4} = 3600$$

The total entries sum is $T_{100} := 90000 = 300^2$. It satisfies the **Pythagoras Theorem** given as $300^2 + 400^2 = 500^2$.

12 Magic Square of Order 11

This subsection brings three types of magic squares of order 11. One as **pandiagonal** without any block. The second and third types are **block-bordered** magic square with same magic sums. One with **consecutive odd numbers** entries and another with **consecutive natural numbers** entries.

12.1 Consecutive Odd Number Entries

According to distribution

$$(319, 360, 481) \Rightarrow \{11, 721, 961, 9251, 101761 = 319^2\},$$

given in 11th line of (16), we can construct a **pandiagonal** magic square of order 11 of **consecutive odd numbers**, 721, 723, ..., 959, 961. See below:

Example 12.1. The **pandiagonal** magic square of order 11 for the **consecutive odd numbers** entries 721, 723, ..., 959, 961 is given by

		9251	9251	9251	9251	9251	9251	9251	9251	9251	9251	9251
	721	761	779	797	815	833	873	891	909	927	945	9251
9251	921	961	737	755	773	791	809	849	867	885	903	9251
9251	879	897	937	955	731	749	767	807	825	843	861	9251
9251	837	855	895	913	931	949	725	743	783	801	819	9251
9251	795	813	831	871	889	907	925	943	741	759	777	9251
9251	753	771	789	829	847	865	883	901	919	959	735	9251
9251	953	729	747	765	805	823	841	859	877	917	935	9251
9251	911	929	947	723	763	781	799	817	835	853	893	9251
9251	869	887	905	923	941	739	757	775	793	811	851	9251
9251	827	845	863	881	899	939	957	733	751	769	787	9251
9251	785	803	821	839	857	875	915	933	951	727	745	9251
	9251	9251	9251	9251	9251	9251	9251	9251	9251	9251	9251	9251

Above magic square is with magic sum, $S_{11 \times 11} := 9251$ with entries sum a perfect square sum, i.e., $T_{121} := 9251 \times 11 = 101761 = 319^2$. It satisfies the **Pythagoras Theorem** given as $319^2 + 360^2 = 481^2$.

Example 12.2. The **block-bordered** magic square of order 11 with inner part as **block-wise** magic square of order 9 for the **consecutive odd numbers** entries 721, 723, ..., 959, 961 is given by

743	759	755	751	747	945	947	951	955	959	739
961	803	901	819	813	887	823	799	897	827	721
957	829	801	893	815	805	903	825	809	889	725
953	891	821	811	895	831	797	899	817	807	729
949	839	775	909	849	761	913	835	771	917	733
741	919	837	767	905	841	777	915	845	763	941
745	765	911	847	769	921	833	773	907	843	937
749	875	865	783	885	851	787	871	861	791	933
753	793	873	857	779	877	867	789	881	853	929
757	855	785	883	859	795	869	863	781	879	925
943	923	927	931	935	737	735	731	727	723	939

The above **block-bordered** magic square of order 11 is with inner part as **block-wise pandiagonal** magic square of order 9 with blocks of **semi-magic** squares of order 3 having equal **semi-magic** sums. Below are respective magic sums:

$$S_{11 \times 11} = 9251$$

$$S_{9 \times 9} = 7569$$

$$Sm_{3 \times 3} = 2523$$

12.2 Consecutive Natural Number Entries

The **block-bordered** magic square given in Example 15.2 is constructed with **consecutive odd numbers** entries [721, 723, ..., 959, 961](#). Still, we can get same magic square sum with **consecutive natural numbers** entries considering as [781, 782, ..., 900, 901](#). See below magic square:

Example 12.3. *The **block-bordered** magic square of order 11 with inner part as **block-wise** magic square of order 9 for the **consecutive natural numbers** entries [781, 782, ..., 900, 901](#) is given by*

792	800	798	796	794	893	894	896	898	900	790
901	822	871	830	827	864	832	820	869	834	781
899	835	821	867	828	823	872	833	825	865	783
897	866	831	826	868	836	819	870	829	824	785
895	840	808	875	845	801	877	838	806	879	787
791	880	839	804	873	841	809	878	843	802	891
793	803	876	844	805	881	837	807	874	842	889
795	858	853	812	863	846	814	856	851	816	887
797	817	857	849	810	859	854	815	861	847	885
799	848	813	862	850	818	855	852	811	860	883
892	882	884	886	888	789	788	786	784	782	890

The magic squares of order 11 given in Examples 12.1, 15.2 and 15.3 are of equal magic sums, i.e., $S_{11 \times 11} := 9251$.

13 Magic Square of Order 12

According to distribution

$$(336, 320, 464) \Rightarrow \{12, 641, 927, 9408, 112896 = 336^2\},$$

given in 12th line of (16), we can construct a **pandiagonal** magic square of order 12 of **consecutive odd numbers**, 641, 643, ..., 925, 927. See below:

Example 13.1. A **block-wise** magic square of order 12 for the entries 641, 643, ..., 925, 927 is given by

		9408	9408	9408	9408	9408	9408	9408	9408	9408	9408	9408	9408
	749	855	641	891	751	853	643	889	753	851	645	887	9408
9408	675	857	783	821	673	859	781	823	671	861	779	825	9408
9408	927	677	819	713	925	679	817	715	923	681	815	717	9408
9408	785	747	893	711	787	745	895	709	789	743	897	707	9408
9408	755	849	647	885	757	847	649	883	759	845	651	881	9408
9408	669	863	777	827	667	865	775	829	665	867	773	831	9408
9408	921	683	813	719	919	685	811	721	917	687	809	723	9408
9408	791	741	899	705	793	739	901	703	795	737	903	701	9408
9408	761	843	653	879	763	841	655	877	765	839	657	875	9408
9408	663	869	771	833	661	871	769	835	659	873	767	837	9408
9408	915	689	807	725	913	691	805	727	911	693	803	729	9408
9408	797	735	905	699	799	733	907	697	801	731	909	695	9408
	9408	9408	9408	9408	9408	9408	9408	9408	9408	9408	9408	9408	9408

The magic sum is $S_{12 \times 12} := 9408$ with entries sums a perfect square sum, i.e., $T_{144} := 9408 \times 12 = 112896 = 336^2$. Moreover, each block of order 4 is **pandiagonal** magic square with equal magic sums, $S_{4 \times 4} := 3136$. It satisfies the **Pythagoras Theorem** given $336^2 + 320^2 = 464^2$.

14 Magic Square of Order 13

This subsection brings three types of magic squares of order 13. One as **pandiagonal** without any block and with **consecutive odd numbers** entries. The second and third types are **block-bordered** magic square with same magic sums. One with **consecutive odd numbers** entries and another with **consecutive natural numbers** entries.

14.1 Consecutive Odd Number Entries

According to distribution

$$(351, 280, 449) \Rightarrow \{13, 561, 897, 9477, 123201 = 351^2\},$$

given in 13th line of (16), we can construct a magic square of order 13 of **consecutive odd numbers**, 561, 563, ..., 895, 897. See below:

Example 14.1. A **pandiagonal** magic square of order 13 for the entries 561, 563, ..., 895, 897 is given by

		9477	9477	9477	9477	9477	9477	9477	9477	9477	9477	9477	9477	9477
	561	609	631	653	675	697	719	767	789	811	833	855	877	9477
9477	849	897	581	603	625	647	669	691	739	761	783	805	827	9477
9477	799	821	869	891	575	597	619	641	689	711	733	755	777	9477
9477	749	771	819	841	863	885	569	591	613	661	683	705	727	9477
9477	699	721	743	791	813	835	857	879	563	611	633	655	677	9477
9477	649	671	693	741	763	785	807	829	851	873	583	605	627	9477
9477	599	621	643	665	713	735	757	779	801	823	871	893	577	9477
9477	887	571	593	615	663	685	707	729	751	773	795	843	865	9477
9477	837	859	881	565	587	635	657	679	701	723	745	793	815	9477
9477	787	809	831	853	875	585	607	629	651	673	695	717	765	9477
9477	737	759	781	803	825	847	895	579	601	623	645	667	715	9477
9477	687	709	731	753	775	797	845	867	889	573	595	617	639	9477
9477	637	659	681	703	725	747	769	817	839	861	883	567	589	9477
	9477	9477	9477	9477	9477	9477	9477	9477	9477	9477	9477	9477	9477	9477

Above magic square is with magic sum, $S_{13 \times 13} := 9477$ with entries sum a perfect square sum, i.e., $T_{169} := 9477 \times 13 = 123201 = 351^2$. It satisfies the **Pythagoras Theorem** given as $351^2 + 280^2 = 449^2$.

Example 14.2. The *block-bordered* magic square of order 13 with inner part as *block-wise* magic square of order 9 for the *consecutive odd numbers* entries 561, 563, ..., 895, 897 is given by

871	853	857	861	865	869	873	577	573	569	565	561	583
563	631	647	643	639	635	833	835	839	843	847	627	895
567	849	691	789	707	701	775	711	687	785	715	609	891
571	845	717	689	781	703	693	791	713	697	777	613	887
575	841	779	709	699	783	719	685	787	705	695	617	883
579	837	727	663	797	737	649	801	723	659	805	621	879
581	629	807	725	655	793	729	665	803	733	651	829	877
867	633	653	799	735	657	809	721	661	795	731	825	591
863	637	763	753	671	773	739	675	759	749	679	821	595
859	641	681	761	745	667	765	755	677	769	741	817	599
855	645	743	673	771	747	683	757	751	669	767	813	603
851	831	811	815	819	823	625	623	619	615	611	827	607
875	605	601	597	593	589	585	881	885	889	893	897	587

The above **block-bordered** magic square of order 13 is with inner part as **block-wise pandiagonal** magic square of order 9 with blocks of **semi-magic** squares of order 3 having equal **semi-magic** sums. Below are respective magic sums:

$$S_{13 \times 13} = 9477$$

$$S_{11 \times 11} = 8019$$

$$S_{9 \times 9} = 6561$$

$$Sm_{3 \times 3} = 2187$$

14.2 Consecutive Natural Number Entries

The **block-bordered** magic square given in Example 14.2 is constructed with **consecutive odd numbers** entries 561, 563, ..., 895, 897. Still, we can get same magic square sum with **consecutive natural numbers** entries considering as 645, 646, ..., 812, 813. See below magic square:

Example 14.3. The **block-bordered** magic square of order 13 with inner part as **block-wise** magic square of order 9 for the **consecutive natural numbers** entries 645, 646, ..., 812, 813 is given by

800	791	793	795	797	799	801	653	651	649	647	645	656
646	680	688	686	684	682	781	782	784	786	788	678	812
648	789	710	759	718	715	752	720	708	757	722	669	810
650	787	723	709	755	716	711	760	721	713	753	671	808
652	785	754	719	714	756	724	707	758	717	712	673	806
654	783	728	696	763	733	689	765	726	694	767	675	804
655	679	768	727	692	761	729	697	766	731	690	779	803
798	681	691	764	732	693	769	725	695	762	730	777	660
796	683	746	741	700	751	734	702	744	739	704	775	662
794	685	705	745	737	698	747	742	703	749	735	773	664
792	687	736	701	750	738	706	743	740	699	748	771	666
790	780	770	772	774	776	677	676	674	672	670	778	668
802	667	665	663	661	659	657	805	807	809	811	813	658

The magic squares of order 13 given in Examples 14.1, 14.2 and 14.3 are of equal magic sums, i.e., $S_{13 \times 13} := 9477$.

14.3 Consecutive Natural Number Entries

15 Magic Square of Order 14

According to distribution

$$(364, 240, 436) \Rightarrow \{14, 481, 871, 9464, 132496 = 364^2\},$$

given in 14th line of (16), we can construct a magic square of order 14 of **consecutive odd numbers**, 481, 483, ..., 869, 871. See below:

Example 15.1. A *block-bordered* magic square of order 14 for the entries 481, 483, ..., 869, 871 is given by

														9464
481	669	861	703	755	635	595	543	513	797	771	835	729	577	9464
773	511	699	831	855	733	653	713	487	585	619	645	555	805	9464
731	803	541	753	823	605	639	491	573	531	673	677	777	847	9464
859	701	779	571	789	709	489	633	547	819	525	671	759	613	9464
807	647	589	503	721	651	537	681	745	603	825	529	851	775	9464
687	499	657	553	521	811	837	787	869	627	567	747	597	705	9464
517	549	743	593	485	785	871	809	839	663	723	581	623	683	9464
569	609	621	659	551	865	783	841	815	717	739	483	685	527	9464
539	565	599	625	667	843	813	867	781	693	493	715	523	741	9464
615	767	791	533	629	575	689	665	719	751	845	563	501	821	9464
641	853	829	707	617	515	749	583	649	507	691	765	799	559	9464
757	827	495	801	763	695	711	509	637	849	557	601	587	675	9464
833	737	725	863	591	545	519	607	679	761	643	795	661	505	9464
655	727	535	769	697	497	579	735	611	561	793	857	817	631	9464
9464	9464	9464	9464	9464	9464	9464	9464	9464	9464	9464	9464	9464	9464	9464

Above magic square is with magic sum, $S_{14 \times 14} := 9464$ with entries sum a perfect square sum, i.e., $T_{196} := 9464 \times 14 = 132496 = 364^2$. It satisfies the **Pythagoras Theorem** given as $364^2 + 240^2 = 436^2$.

Example 15.2. The **block-bordered** magic square of order 11 with inner part as **block-wise** magic square of order 9 for the **consecutive odd numbers** entries 721, 723, ..., 959, 961 is given by

743	759	755	751	747	945	947	951	955	959	739
961	803	901	819	813	887	823	799	897	827	721
957	829	801	893	815	805	903	825	809	889	725
953	891	821	811	895	831	797	899	817	807	729
949	839	775	909	849	761	913	835	771	917	733
741	919	837	767	905	841	777	915	845	763	941
745	765	911	847	769	921	833	773	907	843	937
749	875	865	783	885	851	787	871	861	791	933
753	793	873	857	779	877	867	789	881	853	929
757	855	785	883	859	795	869	863	781	879	925
943	923	927	931	935	737	735	731	727	723	939

The above **block-bordered** magic square of order 11 is with inner part as **block-wise pandiagonal** magic square of order 9 with blocks of **semi-magic** squares of order 3 having equal **semi-magic** sums. Below are respective magic sums:

$$S_{11 \times 11} = 9251$$

$$S_{9 \times 9} = 7569$$

$$Sm_{3 \times 3} = 2523$$

15.1 Consecutive Natural Number Entries

The **block-bordered** magic square given in Example 15.2 is constructed with **consecutive odd numbers** entries [721, 723, ..., 959, 961](#). Still, we can get same magic square sum with **consecutive natural numbers** entries considering as [781, 782, ..., 900, 901](#). See below magic square:

Example 15.3. *The **block-bordered** magic square of order 11 with inner part as **block-wise** magic square of order 9 for the **consecutive natural numbers** entries [781, 782, ..., 900, 901](#) is given by*

792	800	798	796	794	893	894	896	898	900	790
901	822	871	830	827	864	832	820	869	834	781
899	835	821	867	828	823	872	833	825	865	783
897	866	831	826	868	836	819	870	829	824	785
895	840	808	875	845	801	877	838	806	879	787
791	880	839	804	873	841	809	878	843	802	891
793	803	876	844	805	881	837	807	874	842	889
795	858	853	812	863	846	814	856	851	816	887
797	817	857	849	810	859	854	815	861	847	885
799	848	813	862	850	818	855	852	811	860	883
892	882	884	886	888	789	788	786	784	782	890

The magic squares of order 13 given in Examples 14.1, 14.2 and 14.3 are of equal magic sums, i.e., $S_{13 \times 13} := 9464$.

15.2 Block-Bordered Magic Squares of Order 14

Example 15.4. *The **block-bordered** magic square of order 14 with inner part as **block-wise** magic square of order 12 for the **consecutive odd numbers** entries [481, 483, ..., 869, 871](#) is given by*

507	495	855	499	851	503	871	493	843	511	839	515	835	847
869	641	747	533	783	643	745	535	781	645	743	537	779	483
485	567	749	675	713	565	751	673	715	563	753	671	717	867
865	819	569	711	605	817	571	709	607	815	573	707	609	487
489	677	639	785	603	679	637	787	601	681	635	789	599	863
861	647	741	539	777	649	739	541	775	651	737	543	773	491
833	561	755	669	719	559	757	667	721	557	759	665	723	519
821	813	575	705	611	811	577	703	613	809	579	701	615	531
529	683	633	791	597	685	631	793	595	687	629	795	593	823
825	653	735	545	771	655	733	547	769	657	731	549	767	527
525	555	761	663	725	553	763	661	727	551	765	659	729	827
829	807	581	699	617	805	583	697	619	803	585	695	621	523
521	689	627	797	591	691	625	799	589	693	623	801	587	831
505	857	497	853	501	849	481	859	509	841	513	837	517	845

The above **block-bordered** magic square of order 14 is with inner part as **block-wise pandiagonal** magic square of order 12 with blocks of **pandiagonal** magic squares of order 4 having equal magic sums. Below are respective magic sums:

$$S_{14 \times 14} = 9464$$

$$S_{12 \times 12} = 8112$$

$$S_{4 \times 4} = 2704$$

The total entries sum is $T_{196} := 9464 \times 14 = 132496 = 364^2$. It satisfies the **Pythagoras Theorem** given as $364^2 + 240^2 = 436^2$.

16 Magic Square of Order 15

This subsection brings two types of magic squares with same magic sum. One with **consecutive odd numbers** entries and another with **consecutive natural numbers** entries.

16.1 Consecutive Odd Number Entries

According to distribution

$$(375, 200, 425) \Rightarrow \{15, 401, 849, 9375, 140625 = 375^2\},$$

given in 15th line of (16), we can construct a **pandiagonal** magic square of order 15 of **consecutive odd numbers**, 401, 403, ..., 847, 849. See below:

Example 16.1. A **block-wise pandiagonal** magic square of order 15 for the entries 401, 403, ..., 847, 849 is given by

		9375	9375	9375	9375	9375	9375	9375	9375	9375	9375	9375	9375	9375	9375	9375
	401	573	621	755	775	405	571	619	757	773	403	569	617	759	777	9375
9375	741	785	415	551	633	739	787	413	555	631	737	789	417	553	629	9375
9375	565	611	753	771	425	563	615	751	769	427	567	613	749	767	429	9375
9375	783	411	575	625	731	781	409	577	623	735	779	407	579	627	733	9375
9375	635	745	761	423	561	637	743	765	421	559	639	747	763	419	557	9375
9375	461	543	591	725	805	465	541	589	727	803	463	539	587	729	807	9375
9375	711	815	475	521	603	709	817	473	525	601	707	819	477	523	599	9375
9375	535	581	723	801	485	533	585	721	799	487	537	583	719	797	489	9375
9375	813	471	545	595	701	811	469	547	593	705	809	467	549	597	703	9375
9375	605	715	791	483	531	607	713	795	481	529	609	717	793	479	527	9375
9375	431	513	651	695	835	435	511	649	697	833	433	509	647	699	837	9375
9375	681	845	445	491	663	679	847	443	495	661	677	849	447	493	659	9375
9375	505	641	693	831	455	503	645	691	829	457	507	643	689	827	459	9375
9375	843	441	515	655	671	841	439	517	653	675	839	437	519	657	673	9375
9375	665	685	821	453	501	667	683	825	451	499	669	687	823	449	497	9375
	9375	9375	9375	9375	9375	9375	9375	9375	9375	9375	9375	9375	9375	9375	9375	9375

Above magic square is with magic sum, $S_{15 \times 15} := 9375$ with entries sum a perfect square sum, i.e., $T_{225} := 9375 \times 15 = 140625 = 375^2$. Moreover, each block of order 5 is a **pandiagonal** magic square with equal magic sums, $S_{5 \times 5} := 3125$. It satisfies the **Pythagoras Theorem** given as $375^2 + 200^2 = 425^2$.

This subsection brings two types of magic squares with same magic sum. One with **consecutive odd numbers** entries and another with **consecutive natural numbers** entries.

16.2 Consecutive Natural Number Entries

The magic square given in Example 16.2 is constructed with **consecutive odd numbers** entries 401, 403, ..., 847, 849. Still, we can get same magic square sum with **consecutive natural numbers** entries considering as 513, 514, ..., 536, 537. See below magic square:

Example 16.2. A **block-wise pandiagonal** magic square of order 15 for the **consecutive natural numbers** entries 513, 514, ..., 536, 537 is given by

		9375	9375	9375	9375	9375	9375	9375	9375	9375	9375	9375	9375	9375	9375	9375
	513	599	623	690	700	515	598	622	691	699	514	597	621	692	701	9375
9375	683	705	520	588	629	682	706	519	590	628	681	707	521	589	627	9375
9375	595	618	689	698	525	594	620	688	697	526	596	619	687	696	527	9375
9375	704	518	600	625	678	703	517	601	624	680	702	516	602	626	679	9375
9375	630	685	693	524	593	631	684	695	523	592	632	686	694	522	591	9375
9375	543	584	608	675	715	545	583	607	676	714	544	582	606	677	716	9375
9375	668	720	550	573	614	667	721	549	575	613	666	722	551	574	612	9375
9375	580	603	674	713	555	579	605	673	712	556	581	604	672	711	557	9375
9375	719	548	585	610	663	718	547	586	609	665	717	546	587	611	664	9375
9375	615	670	708	554	578	616	669	710	553	577	617	671	709	552	576	9375
9375	528	569	638	660	730	530	568	637	661	729	529	567	636	662	731	9375
9375	653	735	535	558	644	652	736	534	560	643	651	737	536	559	642	9375
9375	565	633	659	728	540	564	635	658	727	541	566	634	657	726	542	9375
9375	734	533	570	640	648	733	532	571	639	650	732	531	572	641	649	9375
9375	645	655	723	539	563	646	654	725	538	562	647	656	724	537	561	9375
	9375	9375	9375	9375	9375	9375	9375	9375	9375	9375	9375	9375	9375	9375	9375	9375

The magic squares of order 15 given in Examples 16.2 and ?? are with same magic sums, i.e., $S_{15 \times 15} := 9375$.

17 Magic Square of Order 16

According to distribution

$$(384, 160, 416) \Rightarrow \{16, 321, 831, 9216, 147456 = 384^2\},$$

given in 16th line of (16), we can construct a magic square of order 16 of **consecutive odd numbers**, 321, 323, ..., 829, 831. See below:

• First Approach: Pandiagonal Magic Square of Order 16

Example 17.1. A *block-wise pandiagonal* magic square of order 16 for *consecutive odd numbers* entries 321, 323, ..., 829, 831 is given by

		9216	9216	9216	9216	9216	9216	9216	9216	9216	9216	9216	9216	9216	9216	9216	9216
	533	635	357	779	503	665	391	745	561	607	321	815	467	701	419	717	9216
9216	363	773	539	629	393	743	505	663	335	801	575	593	429	707	477	691	9216
9216	795	373	619	517	761	407	649	487	831	337	591	545	733	435	685	451	9216
9216	613	523	789	379	647	489	759	409	577	559	817	351	675	461	723	445	9216
9216	563	605	323	813	465	703	417	719	535	633	359	777	501	667	389	747	9216
9216	333	803	573	595	431	705	479	689	361	775	537	631	395	741	507	661	9216
9216	829	339	589	547	735	433	687	449	793	375	617	519	763	405	651	485	9216
9216	579	557	819	349	673	463	721	447	615	521	791	377	645	491	757	411	9216
9216	471	697	423	713	565	603	325	811	499	669	387	749	529	639	353	783	9216
9216	425	711	473	695	331	805	571	597	397	739	509	659	367	769	543	625	9216
9216	729	439	681	455	827	341	587	549	765	403	653	483	799	369	623	513	9216
9216	679	457	727	441	581	555	821	347	643	493	755	413	609	527	785	383	9216
9216	497	671	385	751	531	637	355	781	469	699	421	715	567	601	327	809	9216
9216	399	737	511	657	365	771	541	627	427	709	475	693	329	807	569	599	9216
9216	767	401	655	481	797	371	621	515	731	437	683	453	825	343	585	551	9216
9216	641	495	753	415	611	525	787	381	677	459	725	443	583	553	823	345	9216
	9216	9216	9216	9216	9216	9216	9216	9216	9216	9216	9216	9216	9216	9216	9216	9216	9216

Above magic square is **pandiagonal** with magic sum, $S_{16 \times 16} := 9216$ with entries sum a perfect square sum, i.e., $T_{256} := 9216 \times 16 = 147456 = 384^2$. All the 4×4 blocks are **pandiagonal** magic square of order 4 with equal magic sums, $S_{4 \times 4} = 2304$. It satisfies the **Pythagoras Theorem** given as $384^2 + 160^2 = 416^2$.

• **Second Approach: Bimagic Square of Order 16**

Example 17.2. A *bimagic square* of order 16 for the *consecutive odd numbers* entries 321, 323, ..., 829, 831 is given by

																9216
321	627	797	559	365	607	817	515	407	677	715	505	443	649	743	469	9216
783	573	339	609	803	529	383	589	729	491	389	695	757	455	425	667	9216
563	769	623	349	543	813	579	369	485	727	697	395	457	763	661	423	9216
637	335	545	787	593	355	525	831	683	409	503	709	647	437	475	745	9216
411	681	711	501	439	645	747	473	333	639	785	547	353	595	829	527	9216
725	487	393	699	761	459	421	663	771	561	351	621	815	541	371	577	9216
489	731	693	391	453	759	665	427	575	781	611	337	531	801	591	381	9216
679	405	507	713	651	441	471	741	625	323	557	799	605	367	513	819	9216
429	671	753	451	385	691	733	495	379	585	807	533	343	613	779	569	9216
739	465	447	653	719	509	403	673	821	519	361	603	793	555	325	631	9216
479	749	643	433	499	705	687	413	521	827	597	359	549	791	633	331	9216
657	419	461	767	701	399	481	723	583	373	539	809	619	345	567	773	9216
375	581	811	537	347	617	775	565	417	659	765	463	397	703	721	483	9216
825	523	357	599	789	551	329	635	751	477	435	641	707	497	415	685	9216
517	823	601	363	553	795	629	327	467	737	655	445	511	717	675	401	9216
587	377	535	805	615	341	571	777	669	431	449	755	689	387	493	735	9216
9216	9216	9216	9216	9216	9216	9216	9216	9216	9216	9216	9216	9216	9216	9216	9216	9216

Above magic square is with **bimagic** with magic sums, $S_{16 \times 16} := 9216$ and $Sb_{16 \times 16} := 5657936$. The sum of entries a perfect square sum, i.e., $T_{256} := 9216 \times 16 = 147456 = 384^2$. All the 4×4 blocks are equal of sums entries, i.e., $T_{16} = 9216$. It satisfies the **Pythagoras Theorem** given as $384^2 + 160^2 = 416^2$.

18 Magic Square of Order 17

This subsection brings three types of magic squares of order 17. One as **pandiagonal** without any block and with **consecutive odd numbers** entries. The second and third types are **block-bordered** magic square with same magic sums. One with **consecutive odd numbers** entries and another with **consecutive natural numbers** entries.

18.1 Consecutive Odd Number Entries

According to distribution

$$(391, 120, 409) \Rightarrow \{17, 241, 817, 8993, 152881 = 391^2\},$$

given in 17th line of (16), we can construct a **pandiagonal** magic square of order 17 of **consecutive odd numbers**, 241, 243, ..., 815, 817. See below:

Example 18.1. A *pandiagonal* magic square of order 17 for *consecutive odd numbers* entries 241, 243, ..., 815, 817 is given by

		8993	8993	8993	8993	8993	8993	8993	8993	8993	8993	8993	8993	8993	8993	8993	8993	8993
	241	305	335	365	395	425	455	485	515	579	609	639	669	699	729	759	789	8993
8993	753	817	269	299	329	359	389	419	449	479	543	573	603	633	663	693	723	8993
8993	687	717	781	811	263	293	323	353	383	413	477	507	537	567	597	627	657	8993
8993	621	651	715	745	775	805	257	287	317	347	377	441	471	501	531	561	591	8993
8993	555	585	615	679	709	739	769	799	251	281	311	375	405	435	465	495	525	8993
8993	489	519	549	613	643	673	703	733	763	793	245	275	339	369	399	429	459	8993
8993	423	453	483	513	577	607	637	667	697	727	757	787	273	303	333	363	393	8993
8993	357	387	417	447	511	541	571	601	631	661	691	721	751	815	267	297	327	8993
8993	291	321	351	381	411	475	505	535	565	595	625	655	685	749	779	809	261	8993
8993	803	255	285	315	345	409	439	469	499	529	559	589	619	649	713	743	773	8993
8993	737	767	797	249	279	309	373	403	433	463	493	523	553	583	647	677	707	8993
8993	671	701	731	761	791	243	307	337	367	397	427	457	487	517	547	611	641	8993
8993	605	635	665	695	725	755	785	271	301	331	361	391	421	451	481	545	575	8993
8993	539	569	599	629	659	689	719	783	813	265	295	325	355	385	415	445	509	8993
8993	473	503	533	563	593	623	653	683	747	777	807	259	289	319	349	379	443	8993
8993	407	437	467	497	527	557	587	617	681	711	741	771	801	253	283	313	343	8993
8993	341	371	401	431	461	491	521	551	581	645	675	705	735	765	795	247	277	8993
	8993	8993	8993	8993	8993	8993	8993	8993	8993	8993	8993	8993	8993	8993	8993	8993	8993	8993

Above magic square is with magic sum, $S_{17 \times 17} := 8993$ with entries sum a perfect square sum, i.e., $T_{289} := 8993 \times 17 = 152881 = 391^2$. It satisfies the **Pythagoras Theorem** given as $391^2 + 120^2 = 409^2$.

Example 18.2. The *block-bordered* magic square of order 17 with inner part as *block-wise* magic square of order 15 for the *consecutive odd numbers* entries 241, 243, ..., 815, 817 is given by

271	815	811	807	803	799	795	791	789	279	283	287	291	295	299	303	275
241	675	433	479	677	451	459	679	453	455	681	431	475	683	427	477	817
245	463	689	435	481	669	437	483	665	439	461	685	441	457	687	443	813
249	449	465	673	429	467	691	425	469	693	445	471	671	447	473	667	809
253	375	703	509	377	721	489	379	723	485	381	701	505	383	697	507	805
257	493	389	705	511	369	707	513	365	709	491	385	711	487	387	713	801
261	719	495	373	699	497	391	695	499	393	715	501	371	717	503	367	797
265	315	733	539	317	751	519	319	753	515	321	731	535	323	727	537	793
785	523	329	735	541	309	737	543	305	739	521	325	741	517	327	743	273
781	749	525	313	729	527	331	725	529	333	745	531	311	747	533	307	277
777	615	403	569	617	421	549	619	423	545	621	401	565	623	397	567	281
773	553	629	405	571	609	407	573	605	409	551	625	411	547	627	413	285
769	419	555	613	399	557	631	395	559	633	415	561	611	417	563	607	289
765	645	343	599	647	361	579	649	363	575	651	341	595	653	337	597	293
761	583	659	345	601	639	347	603	635	349	581	655	351	577	657	353	297
757	359	585	643	339	587	661	335	589	663	355	591	641	357	593	637	301
783	243	247	251	255	259	263	267	269	779	775	771	767	763	759	755	787

The above **block-bordered** magic square of order 17 is with inner part as **block-wise pandiagonal** magic square of order 15 with blocks of **semi-magic** squares of order 3 having equal **semi-magic** sums. Below are respective magic sums:

$$S_{17 \times 17} = 8993$$

$$S_{15 \times 15} = 7935$$

$$Sm_{3 \times 3} = 1587$$

18.2 Consecutive Natural Number Entries

The **block-bordered** magic square given in Example 18.2 is constructed with **consecutive odd numbers** entries 241, 243, ..., 815, 817. Still, we can get same magic square sum with **consecutive natural numbers** entries considering as 385, 386, ..., 672, 673. See below magic square:

Example 18.3. The **block-bordered** magic square of order 17 with inner part as **block-wise** magic square of order 15 for the **consecutive natural numbers**

entries 385, 386, ..., 672, 673 is given by

400	672	670	668	666	664	662	660	659	404	406	408	410	412	414	416	402
385	602	481	504	603	490	494	604	491	492	605	480	502	606	478	503	673
387	496	609	482	505	599	483	506	597	484	495	607	485	493	608	486	671
389	489	497	601	479	498	610	477	499	611	487	500	600	488	501	598	669
391	452	616	519	453	625	509	454	626	507	455	615	517	456	613	518	667
393	511	459	617	520	449	618	521	447	619	510	457	620	508	458	621	665
395	624	512	451	614	513	460	612	514	461	622	515	450	623	516	448	663
397	422	631	534	423	640	524	424	641	522	425	630	532	426	628	533	661
657	526	429	632	535	419	633	536	417	634	525	427	635	523	428	636	401
655	639	527	421	629	528	430	627	529	431	637	530	420	638	531	418	403
653	572	466	549	573	475	539	574	476	537	575	465	547	576	463	548	405
651	541	579	467	550	569	468	551	567	469	540	577	470	538	578	471	407
649	474	542	571	464	543	580	462	544	581	472	545	570	473	546	568	409
647	587	436	564	588	445	554	589	446	552	590	435	562	591	433	563	411
645	556	594	437	565	584	438	566	582	439	555	592	440	553	593	441	413
643	444	557	586	434	558	595	432	559	596	442	560	585	443	561	583	415
656	386	388	390	392	394	396	398	399	654	652	650	648	646	644	642	658

The magic squares of order 17 given in Examples 18.1, 18.2 and 18.3 are of equal magic sums, i.e., $S_{17 \times 17} := 8993$.

19 Magic Square of Order 18

According to distribution

$$(396, 80, 404) \Rightarrow \{18, 161, 807, 8712, 156816 = 396^2\},$$

given in 18th line of (16), we can construct a magic square of order 18 of **consecutive odd numbers**, 161, 163, ..., 805, 807. See below:

Example 19.1. A *block-wise* magic square of order 18 for **consecutive odd numbers** entries 161, 163, ..., 805, 807 is given by

																		8712
161	773	771	737	195	267	163	775	769	739	193	265	165	777	767	741	191	263	8712
699	303	663	305	341	593	697	301	661	307	343	595	695	299	659	309	345	597	8712
591	557	413	447	519	377	589	559	415	445	517	379	587	561	417	443	515	381	8712
483	411	521	555	449	485	481	409	523	553	451	487	479	407	525	551	453	489	8712
269	627	339	629	665	375	271	625	337	631	667	373	273	623	335	633	669	371	8712
701	233	197	231	735	807	703	235	199	229	733	805	705	237	201	227	731	803	8712
167	779	765	743	189	261	169	781	763	745	187	259	171	783	761	747	185	257	8712
693	297	657	311	347	599	691	295	655	313	349	601	689	293	653	315	351	603	8712
585	563	419	441	513	383	583	565	421	439	511	385	581	567	423	437	509	387	8712
477	405	527	549	455	491	475	403	529	547	457	493	473	401	531	545	459	495	8712
275	621	333	635	671	369	277	619	331	637	673	367	279	617	329	639	675	365	8712
707	239	203	225	729	801	709	241	205	223	727	799	711	243	207	221	725	797	8712
173	785	759	749	183	255	175	787	757	751	181	253	177	789	755	753	179	251	8712
687	291	651	317	353	605	685	289	649	319	355	607	683	287	647	321	357	609	8712
579	569	425	435	507	389	577	571	427	433	505	391	575	573	429	431	503	393	8712
471	399	533	543	461	497	469	397	535	541	463	499	467	395	537	539	465	501	8712
281	615	327	641	677	363	283	613	325	643	679	361	285	611	323	645	681	359	8712
713	245	209	219	723	795	715	247	211	217	721	793	717	249	213	215	719	791	8712
8712	8712	8712	8712	8712	8712	8712	8712	8712	8712	8712	8712	8712	8712	8712	8712	8712	8712	8712

Above magic square is with magic sum, $S_{18 \times 18} := 8712$ with entries sum a perfect square sum, i.e., $T_{324} := 8712 \times 18 = 156816 = 396^2$. Moreover each block of order 6 is a magic square with magic sum, $S_{6 \times 6} := 2904$. It satisfies the **Pythagoras Theorem** given as $396^2 + 80^2 = 404^2$.

20 Magic Square of Order 19

This subsection brings three types of magic squares of order 19. One as **pandiagonal** without any block and with **consecutive odd numbers** entries. The second and third types are **block-bordered** magic square with same magic sums. One with **consecutive odd numbers** entries and another with **consecutive natural numbers** entries.

20.1 Consecutive Odd Number Entries

According to distribution

$$(399, 40, 401) \Rightarrow \{19, 81, 801, 8379, 159201 = 399^2\},$$

given in 19th line of (16), we can construct a **pandiagonal** magic square of order 19 of **consecutive odd numbers**, 81, 83, ..., 799, 801. See below:

Example 20.1. A **pandiagonal** magic square of order 19 for **consecutive odd numbers** entries 81, 83, ..., 799, 801 is given by

		8379	8379	8379	8379	8379	8379	8379	8379	8379	8379	8379	8379	8379	8379	8379	8379	8379	8379	8379
	81	153	187	221	255	289	323	357	391	425	497	531	565	599	633	667	701	735	769	8379
8379	729	801	113	147	181	215	249	283	317	351	385	457	491	525	559	593	627	661	695	8379
8379	655	689	761	795	107	141	175	209	243	277	311	383	417	451	485	519	553	587	621	8379
8379	581	615	687	721	755	789	101	135	169	203	237	271	343	377	411	445	479	513	547	8379
8379	507	541	575	647	681	715	749	783	95	129	163	197	269	303	337	371	405	439	473	8379
8379	433	467	501	573	607	641	675	709	743	777	89	123	157	229	263	297	331	365	399	8379
8379	359	393	427	461	533	567	601	635	669	703	737	771	83	155	189	223	257	291	325	8379
8379	285	319	353	387	459	493	527	561	595	629	663	697	731	765	115	149	183	217	251	8379
8379	211	245	279	313	347	419	453	487	521	555	589	623	657	691	763	797	109	143	177	8379
8379	137	171	205	239	273	345	379	413	447	481	515	549	583	617	651	723	757	791	103	8379
8379	785	97	131	165	199	233	305	339	373	407	441	475	509	543	577	649	683	717	751	8379
8379	711	745	779	91	125	159	231	265	299	333	367	401	435	469	503	537	609	643	677	8379
8379	637	671	705	739	773	85	119	191	225	259	293	327	361	395	429	463	535	569	603	8379
8379	563	597	631	665	699	733	767	117	151	185	219	253	287	321	355	389	423	495	529	8379
8379	489	523	557	591	625	659	693	727	799	111	145	179	213	247	281	315	349	421	455	8379
8379	415	449	483	517	551	585	619	653	725	759	793	105	139	173	207	241	275	309	381	8379
8379	341	375	409	443	477	511	545	579	613	685	719	753	787	99	133	167	201	235	307	8379
8379	267	301	335	369	403	437	471	505	539	611	645	679	713	747	781	93	127	161	195	8379
8379	193	227	261	295	329	363	397	431	465	499	571	605	639	673	707	741	775	87	121	8379
	8379	8379	8379	8379	8379	8379	8379	8379	8379	8379	8379	8379	8379	8379	8379	8379	8379	8379	8379	8379

Above magic square is with magic sum, $S_{19 \times 19} := 8379$ with entries sum a perfect square sum, i.e., $T_{361} := 8379 \times 19 = 159201 = 399^2$. It satisfies the **Pythagoras Theorem** given as $399^2 + 40^2 = 401^2$.

Example 20.2. The **block-bordered** magic square of order 19 with inner part as **block-wise pandiagonal** magic square of order 15 for the **consecutive odd numbers** entries 81, 83, ..., 799, 801 is given by

119	151	147	143	139	135	131	127	123	769	771	775	779	783	787	791	795	799	115
801	183	727	723	719	715	711	707	703	701	191	195	199	203	207	211	215	187	81
797	153	217	651	275	453	609	277	591	365	423	549	307	531	395	483	489	729	85
793	157	455	633	219	637	261	425	573	279	577	351	485	513	309	517	381	725	89
789	161	639	247	441	635	243	579	337	411	575	303	519	367	471	515	333	721	93
785	165	621	245	663	249	427	561	305	603	339	397	501	335	543	369	457	717	97
781	169	273	429	607	231	665	363	399	547	291	605	393	459	487	321	545	713	101
777	173	221	649	271	449	615	281	589	361	419	555	311	529	391	479	495	709	105
773	177	451	629	225	641	259	421	569	285	581	349	481	509	315	521	379	705	109
117	697	645	251	439	631	239	585	341	409	571	299	525	371	469	511	329	185	765
121	693	619	241	659	255	431	559	301	599	345	401	499	331	539	375	461	189	761
125	689	269	435	611	229	661	359	405	551	289	601	389	465	491	319	541	193	757
129	685	223	653	267	445	617	283	593	357	415	557	313	533	387	475	497	197	753
133	681	447	625	227	643	263	417	565	287	583	353	477	505	317	523	383	201	749
137	677	647	253	443	627	235	587	343	413	567	295	527	373	473	507	325	205	745
141	673	623	237	655	257	433	563	297	595	347	403	503	327	535	377	463	209	741
145	669	265	437	613	233	657	355	407	553	293	597	385	467	493	323	537	213	737
149	695	155	159	163	167	171	175	179	181	691	687	683	679	675	671	667	699	733
767	731	735	739	743	747	751	755	759	113	111	107	103	99	95	91	87	83	763

The above **block-bordered** magic square of order 17 is with inner part as **block-wise pandiagonal** magic square of order 15 with blocks of **semi-magic** squares of order 3 having equal **semi-magic** sums. Below are respective magic sums:

$$S_{19 \times 19} = 8379$$

$$S_{17 \times 17} = 7497$$

$$S_{15 \times 15} = 6615$$

$$Sm_{5 \times 5} = 2205$$

20.2 Consecutive Natural Number Entries

The **block-bordered** magic square given in Example 20.2 is constructed with **consecutive odd numbers** entries 81, 83, ..., 799, 801. Still, we can get same magic square sum with **consecutive natural numbers** entries considering as 261, 162, ..., 620, 621. See below magic square:

Example 20.3. The *block-bordered* magic square of order 19 with inner part as *block-wise* magic square of order 15 for the *consecutive natural numbers* entries 261, 162, ..., 620, 621 is given by

280	296	294	292	290	288	286	284	282	605	606	608	610	612	614	616	618	620	278
621	312	584	582	580	578	576	574	572	571	316	318	320	322	324	326	328	314	261
619	297	329	546	358	447	525	359	516	403	432	495	374	486	418	462	465	585	263
617	299	448	537	330	539	351	433	507	360	509	396	463	477	375	479	411	583	265
615	301	540	344	441	538	342	510	389	426	508	372	480	404	456	478	387	581	267
613	303	531	343	552	345	434	501	373	522	390	419	471	388	492	405	449	579	269
611	305	357	435	524	336	553	402	420	494	366	523	417	450	464	381	493	577	271
609	307	331	545	356	445	528	361	515	401	430	498	376	485	416	460	468	575	273
607	309	446	535	333	541	350	431	505	363	511	395	461	475	378	481	410	573	275
279	569	543	346	440	536	340	513	391	425	506	370	483	406	455	476	385	313	603
281	567	530	341	550	348	436	500	371	520	393	421	470	386	490	408	451	315	601
283	565	355	438	526	335	551	400	423	496	365	521	415	453	466	380	491	317	599
285	563	332	547	354	443	529	362	517	399	428	499	377	487	414	458	469	319	597
287	561	444	533	334	542	352	429	503	364	512	397	459	473	379	482	412	321	595
289	559	544	347	442	534	338	514	392	427	504	368	484	407	457	474	383	323	593
291	557	532	339	548	349	437	502	369	518	394	422	472	384	488	409	452	325	591
293	555	353	439	527	337	549	398	424	497	367	519	413	454	467	382	489	327	589
295	568	298	300	302	304	306	308	310	311	566	564	562	560	558	556	554	570	587
604	586	588	590	592	594	596	598	600	277	276	274	272	270	268	266	264	262	602

The magic squares of order 19 given in Examples 20.1, 20.2 and 20.3 are of equal magic sums, i.e., $S_{19 \times 19} := 8379$.

20.3 Consecutive Natural Number Entries

21 Magic Square of Order 20

According to distribution

22 Magic Square of Order 21

This subsection brings two types of magic squares with same magic sum. One with **consecutive odd numbers** entries and another with **consecutive natural numbers** entries.

22.1 Consecutive Odd Number Entries

According to distribution

$$(819, 540, 981) \Rightarrow \{21, 1081, 1961, 31941, 670761 = 819^2\},$$

given in 21st line of (16), we can construct a magic square of order 21 of **consecutive odd numbers**, 1081, 1083, ..., 1959, 1961. See below:

Example 22.1. A *block-wise pandiagonal* magic square of order 21 for the **consecutive odd numbers** entries 1081, 1083, ..., 1959, 1961 is given by

The total entries sum is $T_{484} := 31768 \times 22 = 698896 = 836^2$. It satisfies the **Pythagoras Theorem** given as $836^2 + 480^2 = 964^2$.

24 Magic Square of Order 23

This subsection brings two types of magic squares with same magic sum. One with **consecutive odd numbers** entries and another with **consecutive natural numbers** entries.

24.1 Consecutive Odd Number Entries

According to distribution

$$(851, 420, 949) \Rightarrow \{23, 841, 1897, 31487, 724201 = 851^2\},$$

given in 23^{rd} line of (16), we can construct a magic square of order 23 of **consecutive odd numbers**, $841, 843, \dots, 1885, 1897$. See below:

Example 24.1. *The **block-bordered** magic square of order 23 with inner part as **block-wise** magic square of order 21 for the **consecutive odd numbers** entries $841, 843, \dots, 1885, 1897$ is given by*

Pythagoras Theorem given as $851^2 + 420^2 = 949^2$.

24.2 Consecutive Natural Number Entries

The **block-bordered** magic square given in Example 24.1 is constructed with **consecutive odd numbers** entries **841, 843, ..., 1885, 1897**. Still, we can get same magic square sum with **consecutive natural numbers** entries considering as **1105, 1106, ..., 1632, 1633**. See below magic square:

Example 24.2. The *block-bordered* magic square of order 23 with inner part as *block-wise* magic square of order 21 for the *consecutive natural numbers* entries **1105, 1106, ..., 1632, 1633** is given by

1612	1147	1145	1143	1141	1139	1137	1135	1133	1131	1129	1127	1615	1617	1619	1621	1623	1625	1627	1629	1631	1633	1128
1590	1394	1259	1454	1422	1523	1162	1335	1237	1535	1360	1567	1180	1316	1215	1576	1403	1501	1203	1353	1281	1473	1148
1592	1448	1391	1268	1166	1435	1506	1531	1325	1251	1189	1369	1549	1572	1303	1232	1207	1413	1487	1470	1347	1290	1146
1594	1265	1457	1385	1519	1149	1439	1241	1545	1321	1558	1171	1378	1219	1589	1299	1497	1193	1417	1284	1479	1344	1144
1596	1421	1488	1198	1340	1291	1476	1395	1260	1452	1436	1511	1160	1317	1250	1540	1377	1552	1178	1297	1231	1579	1142
1598	1194	1408	1505	1480	1350	1277	1449	1389	1269	1154	1433	1520	1544	1330	1233	1174	1367	1566	1588	1306	1213	1140
1600	1492	1211	1404	1287	1466	1354	1263	1458	1386	1517	1163	1427	1246	1527	1334	1556	1188	1363	1222	1570	1315	1138
1602	1359	1565	1183	1314	1216	1577	1402	1504	1201	1358	1278	1471	1382	1270	1455	1437	1512	1158	1331	1238	1538	1136
1604	1187	1372	1548	1573	1304	1230	1210	1411	1486	1467	1345	1295	1459	1392	1256	1155	1431	1521	1532	1328	1247	1134
1606	1561	1170	1376	1220	1587	1300	1495	1192	1420	1282	1484	1341	1266	1445	1396	1515	1164	1428	1244	1541	1322	1132
1608	1424	1522	1161	1332	1239	1536	1373	1553	1181	1296	1229	1582	1419	1489	1199	1339	1294	1474	1400	1257	1450	1130
1125	1165	1434	1508	1533	1326	1248	1175	1370	1562	1586	1309	1212	1195	1409	1503	1483	1348	1276	1446	1387	1274	1613
1124	1518	1151	1438	1242	1542	1323	1559	1184	1364	1225	1569	1313	1493	1209	1405	1285	1465	1357	1261	1463	1383	1614
1122	1356	1279	1472	1381	1273	1453	1442	1509	1156	1319	1249	1539	1374	1554	1179	1310	1217	1580	1401	1502	1204	1616
1120	1468	1346	1293	1462	1390	1255	1152	1429	1526	1543	1329	1235	1176	1368	1563	1574	1307	1226	1208	1414	1485	1618
1118	1283	1482	1342	1264	1444	1399	1513	1169	1425	1245	1529	1333	1557	1185	1365	1223	1583	1301	1498	1191	1418	1620
1116	1311	1218	1578	1415	1490	1202	1338	1292	1477	1398	1258	1451	1423	1525	1159	1337	1236	1534	1361	1564	1182	1622
1114	1575	1305	1227	1196	1412	1499	1481	1351	1275	1447	1388	1272	1168	1432	1507	1530	1324	1253	1186	1371	1550	1624
1112	1221	1584	1302	1496	1205	1406	1288	1464	1355	1262	1461	1384	1516	1150	1441	1240	1547	1320	1560	1172	1375	1626
1110	1318	1252	1537	1379	1551	1177	1298	1228	1581	1416	1491	1200	1352	1280	1475	1380	1271	1456	1440	1510	1157	1628
1108	1546	1327	1234	1173	1366	1568	1585	1308	1214	1197	1410	1500	1469	1349	1289	1460	1393	1254	1153	1430	1524	1630
1106	1243	1528	1336	1555	1190	1362	1224	1571	1312	1494	1206	1407	1286	1478	1343	1267	1443	1397	1514	1167	1426	1632
1610	1591	1593	1595	1597	1599	1601	1603	1605	1607	1609	1611	1123	1121	1119	1117	1115	1113	1111	1109	1107	1105	1126

The **block-bordered** magic squares of order 23 given in Examples 24.1 and 24.2 are of equal magic sums, i.e., $S_{23 \times 23} := 31487$.

25 Magic Square of Order 24

According to distribution

$$(864, 360, 936) \Rightarrow \{24, 721, 1871, 31104, 746496 = 864^2\},$$

given in 24th line of (16), we can construct a magic square of order 24 of **consecutive odd numbers**, 721, 722, ..., 1870, 1871. See below:

Example 25.1. A *block-wise pandiagonal* magic square of order 24 for the **consecutive odd numbers** entries 721, 722, ..., 1870, 1871 is given by

26 Magic Square of Order 25

This subsection brings two types of magic squares with same magic sum. One with **consecutive odd numbers** entries and another with **consecutive natural numbers** entries.

26.1 Consecutive Odd Number Entries

According to distribution

$$(875, 300, 925) \Rightarrow \{25, 601, 1849, 30625, 765625 = 875^2\},$$

given in 25th line of (16), we can construct a magic square of order 25 of **consecutive odd numbers**, 601, 603, ..., 1847, 1849. See below:

Example 26.1. A *block-wise pandiagonal bimagic* square of order 25 for the **consecutive odd numbers** entries 601, 603, ..., 1847, 1849 is given by

26.2 Consecutive Natural Number Entries

The magic square given in Example 26.1 is constructed with **consecutive odd numbers** entries [601, 603, ..., 1847, 1849](#). Still, we can get same **bimagic** square sum with **consecutive natural numbers** entries considering as [913, 914, ..., 1536, 1537](#). See below magic square:

Example 26.2. *A block-wise pandiagonal bimagic square of order 25 for the consecutive natural numbers entries [913, 914, ..., 1536, 1537](#) is given by*

27 Magic Square of Order 26

According to distribution

$$(884, 240, 916) \Rightarrow \{26, 481, 1831, 30056, 781456 = 884^2\},$$

given in 26th line of (16), we can construct a magic square of order 26 of **consecutive odd numbers**, 481, 483, ..., 1829, 1831. See below:

Example 27.1. The **block-bordered** magic square of order 26 with inner part as magic square of order 24 with blocks of order 4 is given by

sums. Below are respective magic sums:

$$S_{26 \times 26} = 30056$$

$$S_{24 \times 24} = 27774$$

$$S_{4 \times 4} = 4629$$

The total entries sum is $T_{676} := 30056 \times 26 = 781456 = 884^2$. It satisfies the **Pythagoras Theorem** given as $884^2 + 240^2 = 916^2$.

28 Magic Square of Order 27

This subsection brings two types of magic squares with same magic sum. One with **consecutive odd numbers** entries and another with **consecutive natural numbers** entries.

28.1 Consecutive Odd Number Entries

According to distribution

$$(891, 180, 909) \Rightarrow \{27, 361, 1817, 29403, 793881 = 891^2\},$$

given in 27th line of (16), we can construct a magic square of order 27 of **consecutive odd numbers**, 361, 363, ..., 1815, 1817. See below:

Example 28.1. A *block-wise pandiagonal* magic square of order 27 for the *consecutive odd numbers* entries 361, 363, ..., 1815, 1817 is given by

The magic squares of order 27 given in Examples 28.1 and 28.2 are with same magic sums, i.e., $S_{27 \times 27} := 29403$.

29 Magic Square of Order 28

According to distribution

$$(896, 120, 904) \Rightarrow \{28, 241, 1807, 28672, 802816 = 896^2\},$$

given in 28th line of (16), we can construct a magic square of order 28 of **consecutive odd numbers**, 241, 243, ..., 1805, 1807. See below:

Example 29.1. A *block-wise pandiagonal* magic square of order 28 for the **consecutive odd numbers** entries 241, 243, ..., 1805, 1807 is given by

30 Magic Square of Order 29

This subsection brings two types of magic squares with same magic sum. One with **consecutive odd numbers** entries and another with **consecutive natural numbers** entries.

30.1 Consecutive Odd Number Entries

According to distribution

$$(899, 60, 901) \Rightarrow \{29, 121, 1801, 27869, 808201 = 899^2\},$$

given in 29th line of (16), we can construct a magic square of order 29 of **consecutive odd numbers**, 121, 123, ..., 1799, 1801. See below:

Example 30.1. The **block-bordered** magic square of order 29 with inner part as **block-wise** magic square of order 27 for the **consecutive odd numbers** entries 121, 123, ..., 1799, 1801 is given by

magic squares with equal magic sums. Below are respective magic sums:

$$S_{29 \times 29} = 27869$$

$$S_{27 \times 27} = 25947$$

$$S_{9 \times 9} = 8649$$

The sum of nine members of each block of order 3 is the same as of magic square of order 9, i.e., 8649. The total entries sum is $T_{841} := 27869 \times 29 = 808201 = 899^2$. It satisfies the **Pythagoras Theorem** given as $899^2 + 60^2 = 901^2$.

30.2 Consecutive Natural Number Entries

The **block-bordered** magic square given in Example 30.1 is constructed with **consecutive odd numbers** entries [841, 843, ..., 1885, 1897](#). Still, we can get same magic square sum with **consecutive natural numbers** entries considering as [1105, 1106, ..., 1632, 1633](#). See below magic square:

Example 30.2. The **block-bordered** magic square of order 29 with inner part as **block-wise** magic square of order 27 for the **consecutive natural numbers** entries [541, 542, ..., 1380, 1381](#) is given by

In this case, the magic sum is $S_{30 \times 30} := 75000$. All the 25 blocks of order 6 are magic squares with equal magic sums, $S_{6 \times 6} := 1500$. The total entries sum is $T_{900} := 75000 \times 30 = 802816 = 1500^2$. It satisfies the **Pythagoras Theorem** given as $1500^2 + 800^2 = 1700^2$.

32 Magic Square of Order 31

This subsection brings two types of magic squares with same magic sum. One with **consecutive odd numbers** entries and another with **consecutive natural numbers** entries.

32.1 Consecutive Odd Number Entries

According to distribution

$$(1519, 720, 1681) \Rightarrow \{31, 1441, 3361, 74431, 2307361 = 1519^2\},$$

given in 31st line of (16), we can construct a magic square of order 31 of **consecutive odd numbers**, 1441, 1443, ..., 3359, 3361. See below:

Example 32.1. The **block-bordered** magic square of order 31 with inner part as **block-wise** magic square of order 27 for the **consecutive odd numbers** entries 1441, 1443, ..., 3359, 3361 is given by

squares with equal **semi-magic** sums. Below are respective magic sums:

$$S_{31 \times 31} = 74431$$

$$S_{29 \times 29} = 69629$$

$$S_{27 \times 27} = 64827$$

$$Sm_{9 \times 9} = 21609$$

$$Sm_{3 \times 3} = 7203$$

The total entries sum is $T_{961} := 74431 \times 31 = 2307361 = 1519^2$. It satisfies the **Pythagoras Theorem** given as $1519^2 + 720^2 = 1681^2$.

32.2 Consecutive Natural Number Entries

The **block-bordered** magic square given in Example 32.1 is constructed with **consecutive odd numbers** entries 1441, 1443, ..., 3359, 3361. Still, we can get same magic square sum with **consecutive natural numbers** entries considering as 1105, 1106, ..., 1632, 1633. See below magic square:

Example 32.2. The **block-bordered** magic square of order 31 with inner part as **block-wise** magic square of order 27 for the **consecutive natural numbers** entries 1921, 1922, ..., 2880, 2881 is given by

33 Magic Square of Order 32

According to distribution

$$(1536, 640, 1664) \Rightarrow \{32, 1281, 3327, 73728, 2359296 = 1536^2\},$$

given in 32^{nd} line of (16), we can construct a magic square of order 32 of **consecutive odd numbers**, 1281, 1283, ..., 3325, 3327. See below:

Example 33.1. A *block-wise* magic square of order 32 for the *consecutive odd numbers* entries 1281, 1283, ..., 3325, 3327 is given by

34 Magic Square of Order 33

This subsection brings two types of magic squares with same magic sum. One with **consecutive odd numbers** entries and another with **consecutive natural numbers** entries.

34.1 Consecutive Odd Number Entries

According to distribution

$$(1551, 560, 1649) \Rightarrow \{33, 1121, 3297, 72897, 2405601 = 1551^2\},$$

given in 33rd line of (16), we can construct a magic square of order 33 of **consecutive odd numbers**, 1121, 1123, ..., 3295, 3297. See below:

Example 34.1. A *block-wise pandiagonal* magic square of order 33 for the **consecutive odd numbers** entries 1121, 1123, ..., 3295, 3297 is given by

The magic squares of order 33 given in Examples 34.1 and 34.2 are with same magic sums, i.e., $S_{33 \times 33} := 72897$.

35 Magic Square of Order 34

According to distribution

$$(1564, 480, 1636) \Rightarrow \{34, 961, 3271, 71944, 2446096 = 1564^2\},$$

given in 34th line of (16), we can construct a magic square of order 34 of **consecutive odd numbers**, 961, 963, ..., 3269, 3279. See below:

Example 35.1. The **block-bordered** magic square of order 34 with inner part as **pandiagonal** magic square of order 32 with blocks of order 4 is given by

magic squares with equal magic sums. Below are respective magic sums:

$$S_{34 \times 34} = 71944$$

$$S_{32 \times 32} = 67712$$

$$S_{4 \times 4} = 8464$$

The total entries sum is $T_{1156} := 67712 \times 34 = 2446096 = 1564^2$. It satisfies the **Pythagoras Theorem** given as $1564^2 + 480^2 = 1636^2$.

36 Magic Square of Order 35

This subsection brings two types of magic squares with same magic sum. One with **consecutive odd numbers** entries and another with **consecutive natural numbers** entries.

36.1 Consecutive Odd Number Entries

According to distribution

$$(1575, 400, 1625) \Rightarrow \{35, 801, 3249, 70875, 2480625 = 1575^2\},$$

given in 35th line of (16), we can construct a magic square of order 35 of **consecutive odd numbers**, 801, 803, ..., 3247, 3249. See below:

Example 36.1. A *block-wise pandiagonal* magic square of order 35 for the *consecutive odd numbers* entries 801, 803, ..., 3247, 3249 is given by

36.2 Consecutive Natural Number Entries

The magic square given in Example 36.1 is constructed with **consecutive odd numbers** entries [801, 803, ..., 3247, 3249](#). Still, we can get same magic square sum with **consecutive natural numbers** entries considering as [1413, 1415, ..., 2636, 2637](#). See below magic square:

Example 36.2. A *block-wise pandiagonal* magic square of order 33 for the *consecutive natural numbers* entries [1413, 1415, ..., 2636, 2637](#) is given by

37 Magic Square of Order 36

According to distribution

$$(1584, 320, 1616) \Rightarrow \{36, 641, 3231, 69696, 2509056 = 1584^2\},$$

given in 36th line of (16), we can construct a magic square of order 36 of **consecutive odd numbers**, 641, 643, ..., 3229, 3231. See below:

Example 37.1. A *block-wise pandiagonal* magic square of order 36 for the *consecutive odd numbers* entries 641, 643, ..., 3229, 3231 is given by

It is **pandiagonal** magic square of order 36. The magic sums is $S_{36 \times 36} := 69696$. All the 81 blocks of order 4 are **pandiagonal** magic squares with equal magic sums, $S_{4 \times 4} := 7744$. The total entries sum is $T_{1296} := 69696 \times 36 = 2509056 = 1584^2$. It satisfies the **Pythagoras Theorem** given as $1584^2 + 320 = 1616^2$.

38 Magic Square of Order 37

This subsection brings two types of magic squares with same magic sum. One with **consecutive odd numbers** entries and another with **consecutive natural numbers** entries.

38.1 Consecutive Odd Number Entries

According to distribution

$$(1591, 240, 1609) \Rightarrow \{37, 481, 3217, 68413, 2531281 = 1591^2\},$$

given in 37th line of (16), we can construct a magic square of order 37 of **consecutive odd numbers**, 481, 483, ..., 3215, 3217. See below:

Example 38.1. The **block-bordered** magic square of order 37 with inner part as **block-wise** magic square of order 35 for the **consecutive odd numbers** entries 481, 483, ..., 3215, 3217 is given by

magic squares with equal magic sums. Below are respective magic sums:

$$S_{37 \times 37} = 68413$$

$$S_{35 \times 35} = 64715$$

$$S_{7 \times 7} = 12943$$

The total entries sum is $T_{1369} := 68413 \times 37 = 2531281 = 1591^2$. It satisfies the **Pythagoras Theorem** given as $1591^2 + 240^2 = 1609^2$.

38.2 Consecutive Natural Number Entries

The **block-bordered** magic square given in Example 38.1 is constructed with **consecutive odd numbers** entries $481, 483, \dots, 3215, 3217$. Still, we can get same magic square sum with **consecutive natural numbers** entries considering as $1165, 1166, \dots, 2532, 2533$. See below magic square:

Example 38.2. *The **block-bordered** magic square of order 37 with inner part as **block-wise** magic square of order 35 for the **consecutive natural numbers** entries $1165, 1166, \dots, 2532, 2533$ is given by*

39 Magic Square of Order 38

According to distribution

$$(1596, 160, 1604) \Rightarrow \{38, 321, 3207, 67032, 2547216 = 1596^2\},$$

given in 38th line of (16), we can construct a magic square of order 38 of **consecutive odd numbers**, 321, 323, ..., 3205, 3207. See below:

Example 39.1. The **block-bordered** magic square of order 38 with inner part as **pandiagonal** magic square of order 36 with blocks of order 4 is given by

magic squares with equal magic sums. Below are respective magic sums:

$$S_{38 \times 38} = 67032$$

$$S_{36 \times 36} = 63504$$

$$S_{4 \times 4} = 7056$$

The total entries sum is $T_{1444} := 67032 \times 38 = 2547216 = 1596^2$. It satisfies the **Pythagoras Theorem** given as $1596^2 + 160^2 = 1604^2$.

40 Magic Square of Order 39

This subsection brings two types of magic squares with same magic sum. One with **consecutive odd numbers** entries and another with **consecutive natural numbers** entries.

40.1 Consecutive Odd Number Entries

According to distribution

$$(1599, 80, 1601) \Rightarrow \{39, 161, 3201, 65559, 2556801 = 1599^2\},$$

given in 39th line of (16), we can construct a magic square of order 39 of **consecutive odd numbers**, 161, 163, ..., 3199, 3201. See below:

Example 40.1. A *block-wise pandiagonal* magic square of order 39 for the *consecutive odd numbers* entries 161, 163, ..., 3199, 3201 is given by

The magic squares of order 39 given in Examples 40.2 and ?? are with same magic sums, i.e., $S_{39 \times 39} := 65559$.

41 Magic Square of Order 40

According to distribution

$$(2400, 1000, 2600) \Rightarrow \{40, 2001, 5199, 144000, 5760000 = 2400^2\},$$

given in 40th line of (16), we can construct a magic square of order 40 of **consecutive odd numbers**, 2001, 2003, ..., 5197, 5199. See below:

Example 41.1. A *block-wise pandiagonal* magic square of order 40 for the *consecutive odd numbers* entries 2001, 2003, ..., 5197, 5199 is given by

42 Magic Square of Order 41

This subsection brings two types of magic squares with same magic sum. One with **consecutive odd numbers** entries and another with **consecutive natural numbers** entries.

42.1 Consecutive Odd Number Entries

According to distribution

$$(2419, 900, 2581) \Rightarrow \{41, 1801, 5161, 142721, 5851561 = 2419^2\},$$

given in 41st line of (16), we can construct a magic square of order 41 of **consecutive odd numbers**, 1801, 1803, ..., 5159, 5161. See below

Example 42.1. The **block-bordered** magic square of order 41 with inner part as **block-wise** magic square of order 39 for the **consecutive odd numbers** entries 1801, 1803, ..., 5159, 5161 is given by

magic squares with equal magic sums. Below are respective magic sums:

$$S_{41 \times 41} = 142721$$

$$S_{39 \times 39} = 135759$$

$$S_{13 \times 13} = 45253$$

The total entries sum is $T_{1681} := 142721 \times 41 = 5851561 = 2419^2$. It satisfies the **Pythagoras Theorem** given as $2419^2 + 900^2 = 2581^2$.

42.2 Consecutive Natural Number Entries

The **block-bordered** magic square given in Example 42.1 is constructed with **consecutive odd numbers** entries [1801, 1803, ..., 5159, 5161](#). Still, we can get same magic square sum with **consecutive natural numbers** entries considering as [2641, 2642, ..., 4320, 4321](#). See below magic square:

Example 42.2. *The **block-bordered** magic square of order 41 with inner part as **block-wise** magic square of order 39 for the **consecutive natural numbers** entries [2641, 2642, ..., 4320, 4321](#) is given by*

In this case, the magic sums is $S_{42 \times 42} := 141288$. All the 49 blocks of order 6 are magic squares with equal magic sums, $S_{6 \times 6} := 20184$. The total entries sum is $T_{1764} := 141288 \times 42 = 5934096 = 2436^2$. It satisfies the **Pythagoras Theorem** given as $2436^2 + 800^2 = 2564^2$.

44 Magic Square of Order 43

This subsection brings two types of magic squares with same magic sum. One with **consecutive odd numbers** entries and another with **consecutive natural numbers** entries.

44.1 Consecutive Odd Number Entries

According to distribution

$$(2451, 700, 2549) \Rightarrow \{43, 1401, 5097, 139707, 6007401 = 2451^2\},$$

given in 43^{rd} line of (16), we can construct a magic square of order 43 of **consecutive odd numbers**, 1401, 1403, ..., 5095, 5097. See below

Example 44.1. The **block-bordered** magic square of order 43 with inner part as **block-wise** magic square of order 39 for the **consecutive odd numbers** entries 1401, 1403, ..., 5095, 5097 is given by

The above **block-bordered** magic square of order 41 is with inner part as **block-wise** magic square of order 169 with blocks of orders 3 as **semi-magic** squares with equal **semi-magic** sums. Below are respective magic and **semi-magic** sums:

$$S_{43 \times 43} = 139707$$

$$S_{41 \times 41} = 133209$$

$$S_{39 \times 39} = 126711$$

$$Sm_{3 \times 3} = 9747$$

The total entries sum is $T_{1849} := 139707 \times 43 = 6007401 = 2451^2$. It satisfies the **Pythagoras Theorem** given as $2451^2 + 700^2 = 2549^2$.

44.2 Consecutive Natural Number Entries

The **block-bordered** magic square given in Example 44.1 is constructed with **consecutive odd numbers** entries 1401, 1403, ..., 5095, 5097. Still, we can get same magic square sum with **consecutive natural numbers** entries considering as 2325, 2326, ..., 4172, 4173. See below magic square:

Example 44.2. The **block-bordered** magic square of order 43 with inner part as **block-wise** magic square of order 39 for the **consecutive natural numbers** entries 2325, 2326, ..., 4172, 4173 is given by

The **block-bordered** magic squares of order 43 given in Examples 44.1 and 44.2 are of equal magic sums, i.e., $S_{43 \times 43} := 139707$.

45 Magic Square of Order 44

According to distribution

$$(2464, 600, 2536) \Rightarrow \{44, 1201, 5071, 137984, 6071296 = 2464^2\},$$

given in 44th line of (16), we can construct a magic square of order 44 of **consecutive odd numbers**, 1201, 1203, ..., 5069, 5071. See below

Example 45.1. A *block-wise pandiagonal* magic square of order 44 for the **consecutive odd numbers** entries 1201, 1203, ..., 5069, 5071 is given by

46 Magic Square of Order 45

This subsection brings two types of magic squares with same magic sum. One with **consecutive odd numbers** entries and another with **consecutive natural numbers** entries.

46.1 Consecutive Odd Number Entries

According to distribution

$$(2475, 500, 2525) \Rightarrow \{45, 1001, 5049, 136125, 6125625 = 2475^2\},$$

given in 45th line of (16), we can construct a magic square of order 45 of **consecutive odd numbers**, 1001, 1003, ..., 5047, 5049. See below

Example 46.1. A *block-wise pandiagonal* magic square of order 44 for the **consecutive odd numbers** entries 1001, 1003, ..., 5047, 5049 is given by

magic squares with equal magic sums. Below are respective magic sums:

$$S_{46 \times 46} = 134136$$

$$S_{44 \times 44} = 128304$$

$$S_{4 \times 4} = 11664$$

The total entries sum is $T_{2116} := 134136 \times 46 = 6170256 = 2484^2$. It satisfies the **Pythagoras Theorem** given as $2484^2 + 400^2 = 2516^2$.

48 Magic Square of Order 47

This subsection brings two types of magic squares with same magic sum. One with **consecutive odd numbers** entries and another with **consecutive natural numbers** entries.

48.1 Consecutive Odd Number Entries

According to distribution

$$(2491, 300, 2509) \Rightarrow \{47, 601, 5017, 132023, 6205081 = 2491^2\},$$

given in 47th line of (16), we can construct a magic square of order 47 of **consecutive odd numbers**, 601, 603, ..., 5015, 5017. See below

Example 48.1. The **block-bordered** magic square of order 47 with inner part as **block-wise** magic square of order 45 for the **consecutive odd numbers** entries 601, 603, ..., 5015, 5017 is given by

magic squares with equal magic sums. Below are respective magic sums:

$$S_{47 \times 47} = 132023$$

$$S_{45 \times 45} = 126405$$

$$S_{5 \times 5} = 14045$$

The total entries sum is $T_{2209} := 132023 \times 47 = 6205081 = 2491^2$. It satisfies the **Pythagoras Theorem** given as $2491^2 + 300^2 = 2509^2$.

48.2 Consecutive Natural Number Entries

The **block-bordered** magic square given in Example 48.1 is constructed with **consecutive odd numbers** entries [601, 603, ..., 5015, 5017](#). Still, we can get same magic square sum with **consecutive natural numbers** entries considering as [1705, 1706, ..., 3912, 3913](#). See below magic square:

Example 48.2. *The **block-bordered** magic square of order 47 with inner part as **block-wise** magic square of order 45 for the **consecutive natural numbers** entries [1705, 1706, ..., 3912, 3913](#) is given by*

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